

FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF THE FUNERAL INDUSTRY AS MODERATED BY EXTERNAL FACTORS TOWARDS COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE

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ABSTRACT

The funeral business' services, products, and accommodations are necessary and compulsory. The morbid nature of the funeral industry gave the entrepreneurs profit. The Funeral Industry in the province of Nueva Vizcaya had a primary and standard service of embalming to burial. This study sought to determine the financial performance of the Funeral Industry in Nueva Vizcaya as moderated by external factors towards competitive advantage. In determining the factors affecting good financial performance of Funeral Industry towards competitive advantage, Porter's Five Forces was used as a strategic analytical tool to assess and evaluate the level of intensity of competition in the Funeral Industry. Also, the PESTEL analysis was used to analyze and monitor the macro-environmental factors that had impact on the Funeral Industry. This study employed the quantitative-qualitative approach, particularly the descriptive design of research. Research informants were the owners or managers of the identified funeral parlor businesses, and also key employees upon the referral of the owners or managers were also included. The main mode of gathering data in this study was the conduct of face-to-face interviews. Data gathered were corroborated and utilized by information gathered from the in-depth document-scanning. Findings revealed that the Funeral Industry in Nueva Vizcaya was well-established and had good reputation considering the number of years operating in the business. Their financial performance revealed a strong financial performance which often meant it had growing revenues, and a healthy amount of free cash flow. The external factors such as political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental were factors of good financial performance of the funeral industry towards competitive advantage. The challenges of the funeral industry were in adherence with the government laws and regulations, inflation, flexibility in the deeply ingrained culture, varied traditions, beliefs, and values. Traditional funeral service to contemporary funeral service was highly recommended. The contextualized "Futures Thinking Model" for the funeral industry would be a tool for a re-engineered service of funeral industry in

a direction where they wanted to, understood and valued by consumers, and where their profitability increased.

Keywords: *Funeral Business, Porter's Five Forces, PESTLE, Futures Thinking*

INTRODUCTION

“To live is Christ and to die is gain” (Philippians 1:21)

“Death comes to everyone”. Everyone passes this life one time or another, one way or another. It is our ultimate and final destination.

From one generation to another, different types of business organizations such as the Funeral Industry had long been in existence. The funeral industry addressed and catered to the needs of individuals and the society in general, bereaving for the passing of loved ones (Walter, 2017). The primary concern of the funeral industry was to continue and survive over time, amidst adversity, rapid competitions, and varied preferences of some customers looking for not just the basic nor standard service but eyeing for something beyond the usual service expectations (Weaver, 2016). To achieve their goals and objectives, funeral services business had to constantly adjust to their external environment as what other businesses may likewise adjust with. The environment was very dynamic and constantly changing in nature and so it was a need and a must for Funeral Industry to continuously adapt their objectives for survival purposes, and best yet, to establish a certain identity, a good reputation, and a “name” in comparison with its competitors. Some funeral businesses developed and adopted various techniques and new add-on services were added over time to cope with the threat and challenges of the strategic problems (Derogongan and Agosto, 2019). Considering the current period of global pandemic where innumerable deaths had arisen, funeral industry, though facing profitability concerns prior to this period, had been overwhelmed with the number of customers to serve. Yet, the possibility of being unable to cater to most, if not all, was also a concern on profitability requiring an adequate analysis whether, indeed, the funeral services as a business performed as they were expected to be.

The Funeral Industry

Funerals may be defined as the ritual or ceremonial disposal of a body; the two essential components were therefore a body and a ceremony or ritual. The funeral industry's structure revolved around those who managed the body rather than the ceremony (Walter, 2016). Moreover, the funeral industry services were characterized by their strong emotiveness, non-recurrence, irreversibility, uncommonness, high level of symbolism and personalization, and emotion control because funeral services quality was strongly dependent on funeral industry's integrated logistics, proximity, and integrity. The funeral industry consumers then were strongly emotion-driven at the purchase time. Funeral industry services providers should then find the right balance of emotions to express (Korai and Souiden, 2017).

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The Funeral Industry business was often viewed in shallow depth. However, the services, products, and accommodations they provided were necessary and compulsory. The morbid nature of the Funeral Industry gave the entrepreneur profit from investments. The funeral industry could be divided into three categories: private cemetery owners or operators, funeral homes, and agents of burial and memorial products. (MacMurray and Futrell, 2019). The funeral industry may be morbid but remuneratively lucrative such as some high -end funeral homes, and maybe franchised which was part and parcel of what is now popularly known as the funeral industry. Funeral crematoriums were run and managed like a corporation offering life plans, complete burial packages, benefits, product development, accommodations, and perhaps a dash of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).

The biggest funeral services businesses were the American and were traded on the New York Stock Exchange. There were four American publicly-traded funeral services companies but Service Corporation International (SCI) was by far the biggest. It operated a vast network of 1,423 funeral homes and 374 cemeteries in the US, Canada, and Germany conducting some 300,000 funerals yearly (Lafleur, 2012).

In Asia, there was a rapidly growing aging population, as the funeral service industry developed and the market grew. There was an increasing economic value and interest in funeral services. However, Korea's funeral services were developed in a biased and unfair direction focusing only on funeral services after death. Compared to the situation of advanced funeral services in the United States, the United Kingdom, and Japan, not only the funeral but also the care of the deceased's family and acquaintances were developing (Jinho and Jeungsun, 2020).

Therefore, funeral industry was developing rapidly. The ultimate goal of life was making it a personal necessity to prepare and accept the fact that everyone needed to work on it because it was the ultimate destination of life. Funeral accommodations and death industries were pre-need due to the fact that individuals could not foresee and anticipate when it was their time to die (Hobbs et al., 2022).

The evaluation of competitiveness and sustainability of financial performance of funeral industry showed that management accounting techniques played an important function in creating a sustainable competitive advantage for a funeral industry (Wadesango et al., 2021).

Along with its growth came the need to stay competitive. To stay competitive, there was a need for rapid blow-up and expansion in funeral accommodations sector fueled by various factors such as demographic profile. Funeral industries competed through marketing such as competitiveness and building a good reputation such as being reliable (Halpenny, 2013).

The funeral industry, just like any other industries, was also an organized industry. The National Funeral Directors Association (NFDA) was the world's leading and largest

funeral service association catering and serving to 18,500 individual members who represented nearly 10,000 funeral homes in the United States and 43 countries around the world (nfda.com). In the Philippines, the funeral business members were organized through the Philippine Mortuary Association Inc. consisting of 420 funeral members nationwide advocating policies that would enable healthy growth in the death care sector and provide access to decent death benefits to Filipinos from all walks of life. The organization was headed by Father Renato Dychangco who had been advocating policies that would properly define the mortuary industry and its function in the community (Association-Backs-Bills-Improve-Standards-Death-Care-506811, 2016).

The leading and well-known funeral companies in Manila, Philippines included: (1) Arlington Memorial Chapels and Crematory, Inc. It was founded by Nestor Lopez Jose in 1982 who was previously awarded the Best of the Best Funeral Home in Asia and recognized by the National Funeral Directors Association (NFDA); (2) Sanctuarium. It was awarded as 2004 Philippine Marketing Excellence Award, Most Outstanding Columbarium Complex, 2003 Family & Consumers Choice Awardee, and Most Outstanding Comprehensive Memorial Package. It was the only structure with a mortuary, crematorium, columbarium, religious chapels, and audio-visual archives all in one; (3) Loyola Memorial Chapels & Crematorium, Inc. (LMCCI). The Loyola Memorial was founded by the late senator Gil Puyat in 1972 and was a sub-component of the Loyola Group of Companies which included the Loyola Life Plan. It offered “Premier” and “Super Deluxe” chapels (Guerrero, 2014). It was then described as the most modern and complete complex of 16 memorial chapels and mortuary services set up in Asia. (4) La Funeria Paz. It started with one small chapel built at the corner of Calle Paz (now C.M. Recto Ave.) and Calle Almanza (now T. Mapua St.), in the heart of Binondo. It has remained strong and unwavering in its commitment to continuously provide excellent memorial service. Testament to this, La Funeraria Paz had been privileged to have celebrated the lives of distinguished personages such as Apolinario Mabini, Melchora Aquino, President Diosdado Macapagal, and Vice President Fernando Lopez, to name a few; (5) The Shrine of St. Thérèse of the Child Jesus. It was envisioned to be the center of devotion to the Saint in Asia with 168 basement parking slots which were also conveniently available to the Shrine and Columbarium visitors. The Columbarium also featured an Ecclesiastical Museum where artworks about the life of St. Thérèse were displayed. It also had a security access system in place to ensure the safety and peace of mind of its visitors; (6) Heritage Park (Heritage Memorial Park). It was the country's premier memorial services provider. Services include Garden Monument, Columbarium, Pre-need Interment Plans, Pre-need Cremation Plans, Pre-need Memorial Plans (Full-Body), and Memorial Lots; (7) St. Peter Group of Companies. It was founded by Francisco M. Bautista (1914-1996) and had been in the business for more than 30 years. St. Peter Group of Companies were deathcare experts and the choice of every Filipino in the delivery of world-class deathcare services. The funeral company operated a “high-end” and “elite” memorial chapel in Quezon City, Cebu City, and Davao City. There were memorial chapels in Sta. Mesa, Manila and in Alabang, Metro Manila along with more than 200 chapels nationwide. A corporate profile of the firm also offered an “e-Buro” accommodation which would enable families, relatives, and friends who could not attend to the wake to view the remains anywhere in the world through their website; (8) Mother

Theresa Crematorium and Columbarium. It was a crematorium business only, located in C-3, East Grace Park, Caloocan, Metro Manila; (9) Funeraria Floresco. It was established in 1934, located in 219 Gen Luna, Malabon, Metro Manila; and (10) The Manila American Cemetery and Memorial in the Philippines. The headstones were aligned in 11 plots forming a generally circular pattern. It occupied 152 acres on a prominent plateau, visible at a distance from the east, south, and west. It contained the largest number of graves of dead military personnel of World War II with a total of 16,859 (Sledge, 2005).

In terms of the data on the number of deaths which eventually required the services of funeral services, it had reached 590,709 in 2018, an increase of 2.0 percent from the previous year's 579,237 deaths. This was equivalent to a crude death rate (CDR) of 5.6, or about six (6) persons per thousand population. In 2018, an average of 1,618 persons died daily. This translated to 67 deaths per hour or one (1) per minute (www.psa.com). One of the leading causes of death in the Philippines was ischemic heart disease striking around 88.4 thousand people. The other four leading causes of death were malignant neoplasms, cerebrovascular disease, pneumonia, and diabetes mellitus. Therefore, funeral industry in the Philippines was a large and growing industry. The cost for funeral practice ranged from 416,00 and 520,000 pesos. This business was viewed by most as displeasing, but the products and services they provided were necessary. The morbid nature of the business meant that individuals could profit from investments in funeral industry (San Jose et al., 2022). As it was a known fact that for every product and, or service offered and availed of, corresponding fees or charges entailed. Thus, any business when efficiently managed may lead to a state of profitability. This included the funeral industry businesses.

In Nueva Vizcaya, there were a few funeral businesses. There were only eight (8) registered as identified by the Department of Trade and Industry because of their continuous services and reputation. Among the identified funeral industries were Carbonel Funeral Homes in Bagabag, Christian J Funeral Homes in Bambang, Funeraria Carbonel in Solano, Gambito Funeral Home in Bayombong, Everlasting Funeral Home in Aritao, Dos Hermanos Funeral Home in Solano, Rosete Funeral Home in Quezon, and St. Peter Funeral Home and Chapels in Bayombong.

Nueva Vizcaya has 4,427.248 estimated Land Area (sq. Km) and Population Density based on PPDO-GIS Data with Gross Population Density of 94 per sq. km (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2015 Census). According to the article Registered Deaths in the Philippines (2018), there were 2,670 (5.7%) total deaths (doh.gov.ph). Among the industry groups, funeral and related activities recorded the highest income in the province (Sector S_2017 ASPBI Publication psa.gov.ph, 2017).

The motivation behind studying this sector was the same reason why others engaged into Funeral Industry - death was inevitable and there was revenue in death. Anticipated high profits played a vital role in motivating entry into the sector (Wanjiru, 2001) although in the National level, no profitability study had been conducted because the funeral industries seldom disclosed their financial statements.

Furthermore, no study had been conducted in the region on profitability analysis of funeral industry. Hence, the aim of this study was to explore and examine factors and determinants that affected the profitability growth of the funeral industry in Nueva Vizcaya. It also more broadly contributed to the understanding of the dynamic revenue status and stigma of funeral industry. An entrepreneur from Africa had attained all his wealth through death. Death was therefore profitable (Röschenthaler, 2015).

Funeral industry had attracted little attention as research subject but it was an interesting subject. Although death and industry were both considered subjects of interest, some people considered them contradictory concepts. However, the basis of funeral industry activity was precisely its role in linking death and the industrial and economic context (Tanaka, 2012).

This study would be beneficial to the Department of Trade and Industry as basis for further evaluation of Funeral Homes business in the Province. Funeral industry of Nueva Vizcaya, as they would realize, was a daunting entrepreneurship, yet a doable task. This study may provide additional insights on sustaining this kind of service business.

Factors of Good Financial Performance of Funeral Industry

Earnings, revenue, and sales in particular from funeral homes services may be attributed from the death rate, progressive price increases of products and services, the product mix, and the economy's recent conditions. Subsequently, investors aiming for higher-revenue and above-average earnings tended to make add-on services elsewhere. However, what the funeral industry lacked was prospecting of key-partner businesses with more or less the same field to compensate stability. One of the most deterrent obstacles in this kind of business was skipping out traditional burials especially practices, traditions, and customs towards cremation. This trend had been going on for years at a late stage of acceptance, but at a steady pace. Cremations then tended to lower revenues (Ellig, 2015). This was in the past years, though observations were evident revealing that the cremation option was becoming favorable by some individuals which may present a better picture in terms of a good product offering and, eventually, with good business standing.

The existence of businesses was to generate profits, and that was the main reason why people engaged into business, and funeral companies were no exemption. It was the same but with some humane factor on it because they dealt with sad and grieving emotions of those who were left behind. The funeral industry was a constantly sustainable business because of the clients' prospective which was sending family members passing to the next life. In 2018, there were about 7.56 deaths per 1,000 inhabitants worldwide (statistica.com). Philippines' reported deaths in 2018 reached 590,709, an increase of 2.0 percent from the previous year's 579,237 deaths. This was equivalent to a crude death rate (CDR) of 5.6 or about six (6) persons per thousand population. In 2018, an average of 1,618 persons died daily (psa.gov.ph). As of November 7, 2021, there had been almost 250 million cases of coronavirus (COVID-19) worldwide. The disease had impacted almost every country and territory in the world, with the United States confirming nearly one-fifth of all global cases (who.com). Therefore, the COVID-19 pandemic was subject

to restrictions on funeral sizes and practices (Burrell, 2020). However, just like other business industries, funeral homes had to recognize and distinguish themselves if they were to earn an edge in the market competitively amidst global pandemic, either attract new clients or retain existing clients in the form of families they had served.

According to the World Funeral News of 2021, the world's leading and major funeral home companies encountered sustained growth and general upward economic trend. Despite the drastic effect suffered between the months of March and May, 2020, most had managed to overcome the crisis caused by the Covid-19 global pandemic and were ever ready preparing to face a still uncertain future. Four (4) of the top 10 funeral companies were located in North America, one (1) in Australia, three (3) in Europe, and two (2) in Asia. These were the top 10 funeral home companies in the world: (1) Service Corporation International. The company had a turnover of \$3,230 million with a profit of \$762 million and a gross margin of 23.5% in 2019, multiplying the figures of its immediate rival in the world ranking. This accorded them the ranking of the largest funeral home companies in the world, with the headquarter in Texas, USA; (2) Le Groupe français des services funéraires (OGF). It was the French leader in the Funeral Industry between September, 2019 and September, 2020. It had a turnover of 580 million euros; (3) Matthews International. It was the largest supplier of copper and granite monuments in the United States. Its turnover in 2020 exceeded \$670 million, with a gross profit of \$154.3 million and a gross margin of 23.02%; (4) Invocare. It operated in Australia, New Zealand, and Singapore through its network of over 270 funeral homes and 16 cemeteries and crematoria. It employed around 1,800 people worldwide and had revenues of \$500.35 million in the last year; (5) Co-operative Group Limited. It was the UK's largest consumer cooperative. It included legal and funeral services, insurance, e-pharmacy, and retail and wholesale food businesses. In 2020, it had a turnover of \$293.5 million, with a gross margin of 26.58% and a total amount of 104.6 million gross profit; (6) Dignity Plc. It was one of the leading providers of funeral services and prepaid plans in the UK market, and the company achieved revenues of \$338.9 million and a profit of \$177.2 million by 2019; (7) StoneMor Partners L.P. It was the second largest network of funeral homes and cemeteries in the United States and, according to the company's published balance sheet, the revenues for the third quarter of 2020 were \$76.9 million and the revenues for the last nine months were \$218.8 million; (8) Carriage Service. It was one of the largest funeral home companies in the United States with a sustained and stable growth trend in 2019 which obtained revenues of 274.1 million dollars with 79.59 million of gross profit; (9) Fu Shou Yuan International. Its headquarters was in Shanghai, China. It achieved revenues of \$283 million in 2019, making it one of the largest funeral home companies worldwide; and (10) Nirvana Asia Group. It had headquarters in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Nirvana Asia Group. It was one of Asia's largest funeral home companies in 2019 and had a turnover of 198 million dollars with a gross profit of 50.7 million.

A remarkable number of funeral homes in the United States were family-owned businesses. They contributed to the overall economy and the society throughout generations to create wealth, provide employment opportunities, and serve the communities that surround them. Factors like family succession values and standards, the competitive game, the players, strategies, payoff and rewards were contributors to

the improvement of business continuity and profitability (Austin, 2015). According to the National Funeral Directors Association (NFDA), statistics showed that there were more or less 19,322 funeral homes, approximately 115,000 cemeteries, 1,155 crematoriums, and an estimated 300 coffin sellers (Hemanson, 2013). The total revenue from the funeral industry alone was about \$14.2 billion in 2016 (Lawton, 2016).

One of the most important objectives of any type of business was to earn profit. Secondary to it was increasing market share and increasing sales volume. Obviously, the death industry prided and proved itself in providing recession-proof services because, after all, death was unavoidable, and someone must take in the deceased bodies by providing services to the bereaved families and friends. The vital motivation of entry into the funeral arena was anticipated high profits (Van Cranenburgh, 2014). However, some individuals also engaged into funeral industry to continue operating the businesses inherited from their parents and relatives. However, some also turned to local politics (Rygiel, 2016). Therefore, there was clearly money to be made in the funeral industry and because death was inevitable, there would always be a market everyday (Canning, 2012). This remained as funeral industries' primary source of profit. As an indicator of efficiency, there must be profit. Profit was a financial gain. It was the earnings from sales or revenue after deduction of all costs, including interest payment on debt and tax (Hasanaj, 2019). Therefore, a high profit was an indication that a business was efficiently and effectively utilizing its funds (Ponsian et al., 2014). Due to market liberalization, a business' ability to increase its profit, to survive, and be competitive was more of an issue nowadays (Dereli, 2015).

In the funeral industry, profits were not the only major goal, the company was more concerned with the goals and prospects of the bereaved family. If the customer was satisfied, they would definitely recommend to their family and friends (Beard and Burger, 2017). Feasibility studies proved that the funeral industry business was profitable and, thus, viable (Granada, 2019). The necessity of firms optimizing their level of working capital management and maintaining enough liquidity affected the profitability (Singhania, 2017).

Moreover, in the area of finances, so as to attain right decisions appropriate to the business, management accounting techniques such as capital budgeting, product costing, and forecasting also played important function in creating a sustainable competitive advantage for an organization (Dana et al., 2020). Therefore, funeral businesses likewise needed such concepts and were actually utilized.

External Factors

With respect to external factors, the funeral industry businesses enabled themselves to assert current business situations in order to develop appropriate strategic actions, novel strategies, ability to foresee the future trends in the funeral industry, and appropriate measures must be implemented in advertising, technology and price standardization (Borres, 2020).

The rise of new corporate funerals and the growing trends in technology switched people's demands on how they dealt with death. It was the start of a great challenge on how to compete with the established and well-known giants. Also, less-performing funerals could not cope up with the trend and expenses probably because most people tended to go over to the corporates than the typical local funeraria. Another turning point was the practice of cremation (Derogongan and Agosto, 2019).

Even if it was a satisfactory market, threats could result to unfavorable conditions for the funeral sector development, so the improvement and the correct use of strategy and marketing tools could generate greater efficiency in service, as well as the innovation could be a relevant alternative to avoid better structured competitors (Anacleto et al., 2019). On taking importance in shaping competition in the funeral industry, there were different factors that might be external or internal contributing to how competition was formed among the industry players. Every business firm had a basic structure and foundation, or a set of fundamental economic and technical characteristics that gave rise to these competitive forces. According to Porter et al. (1980), competition was a concern among industries dealing with services as well as those selling products. Coupled with dynamic and fast changing environment, as competition increased, it had become increasingly important also for firms to understand that the type of industry they were engaged into had a need to develop effective strategies to gain competitive advantages in the market.

The funeral industry's performance, behavior, and status were affected by its competitors and their strategic competitiveness. The degree of competitive advantage in the market referred to the degree by which individual firms or businesses in the entire market needed to influence the price or other variables in which the product or services were offered and sold. In the business of funeral services for example, the old-fashioned and traditional funeral industry included services like embalming, coffin, accommodation, and burial in a cemetery which emerged as a result of four sources in American society: Industrial Revolution, Civil War, the advent of a refined code of conduct and practices as a result of incremented wealth and as a result of social prosperity, and transmuting cultural views on death (Burger and Beard, 2015). Nowadays, innovations in their products as well as in delivering services had, over time, been integrated.

As cultural traditions became less strict, change and innovation were expected in the coming years. The brandscapes became more widespread in funeral industry products and services and even contributed to 'themed' funerals and funeral settings (Sanders, 2012). The most common types of funeral settings were traditional funeral service and committal funeral service, also known as graveside service. Also, today's contemporary funeral industry adopted and habituated hearty and convivial social media. The internet itself was a synchronization to both public demands and to the growing understanding of how technologies could be accustomed to secure funeral orchestrating, family grieving and sadness, and remembrance of the dead (Gibbs et al., 2017).

Funeral industry owners needed to embrace and adopt the use of technology not only to get their establishments' name on the Internet but also to reach out costumers

who preferred to compare prices and services in a digital manner. Easy-to-access digital presence was essential for funeral home success and profitability (Beard and Burger, 2017). A funeral and crematorium Industry business in a rural location built social capital, outlining the concept as a fluid and dynamic, time-influenced phenomenon rather than a discrete, fixed network that occasionally created new links. Core social capital described existing bonds between actors within a group while the augmented social capital of inter-group bridging created a more expansive network (Moyes et al., 2015).

Challenges of the Funeral Industry

The rising environmental and ecological concerns felt across the world's communities had, alongside a rapid change of consumer preferences and product expectations, been transforming the core of the funeral service industry. As a result, the digitalization process of funeral homes intensified in the last years in order to incorporate the new market trends. Moreover, the idea that a funeral must be a place to mourn the deceased had become outdated being substituted by a service that allowed the celebration, festively, of the deceased's life (Costa and Oliveria, 2021).

The actual purpose of funeral was to honor the dead for their meritorious services on earth, usher them into eternal glory, and integrate them into the next world. However, there were often some skirmishes that militated against these positive motives. As a result, some families that used to be closely knitted end up being divided (Adu-Gyamfi, 2020). The funeral industry's professionalization of one's laymen pursuits, industrialization, and urbanization changes revealed that culture or 'way of life' was altered, and accordingly, so was the culture of death (Zlomke, 2013).

During this time of pandemic, the context of the public health crisis generated actions and a need to re-adapt the firm's logistics policy for transport, procurement, and inventory in order to ensure continuity of the funeral services rendered without detriment to the consumers of the funeral plans and new clients (de Assunção, 2020).

The combination of high poverty and low political stability aggravated the increasing financial burden of death costs on households prompting them to a more active interference into funeral regulation (Sadigov, 2020). The funerals costs were distress purchases and so debt was the outcome of irrational decisions made while emotionally overwhelmed. These discourses ignored how people might use funeral purchases in dealing with the experience of death as they obscured rather than explained the emotionally infused decision-making that incurred funeral debt (McManus and Schafer, 2014).

The challenges also included political scenario, economic growth, and social relations especially among family. To sustain such business, local government must extend support and protect it against corporate funeral homes, against politicking, and eventual loss of culture and family (Derogongan et al., 2019).

Moreover, the competitors were the main challenge of the funeral industry, while its opportunity included the improvement of services by offering cremation in the future for non-crematorium services providers. Furthermore, funeral industry's corporate social responsibility programs should include programs for the indigents, proper waste disposal, observance of proper hygiene and sanitation, compliance with the Department of Environment and Natural Resources, and government regulations (Granada, 2019).

The funeral industry had grown over the years and with intense competition had found the need to employ sales representatives. In order to increase sales and a customer base, funeral industry had adapted to personal selling which required the need of sales people to be physically in contact with customers (Chikowore, 2017).

Furthermore, restrictive regulations affected the revenues of funeral industry and services to a much greater extent than they affected the revenues of cemeteries and crematories, and in some cases the regulations even increased funeral homes and services' share of industry revenues. Thus, it appeared that funeral industry received most of the benefits of regulation (Ellig, 2015).

The shifts in the practices and beliefs around death were mediated by individuals, households, and businesses who had historical affinity towards movement. The mobile orientation influenced the perception of rites and responsibilities surrounding death, and more mobile 'ways of dying' in turn created new subjectivities and new ways in which to imagine relations between the living and the dead. A steadily more numerous and prominent group of entrepreneurs were well-placed to shape these processes through their role as cultural mediators and technological innovators and their particular emphasis on maintaining a flow of bodies (both dead and alive) between rural and urban areas (de Witte, 2011). Anxiety for death was relatively high compared to the past. The funeral industry played the role of providing meaning, value, and concepts to counter that anxiety. On the other hand, the provision and consumption of modern funeral services were on a teleological level to construct a "desirable death" concept rather than just on the level of an exchange of goods and manpower. But if a funeral industry service was what reflected the concept of the way of life and death, the aforementioned cases obviously showed that the concept of death did not come to exist a priori, coincidentally and ambiguously, and that it could also be generated through a causal relation with creativity in active commercial practices (Tanaka, 2006).

The "Futures Thinking Model"

The "Futures Thinking Model" was a model of strategic foresight based on understanding, anticipating, and shaping the future with applicability to organizations such as Funeral Industry (LugoSantiago, 2020). The key components of the framework included inputs, "foresight" work, outputs, and strategy/policy. It was an approach to strategic design that considered what was likely to change and what was likely to stay the same in the future as a means to be more reflective in strategic planning. It would reveal what could happen as a result of decisions, actions, and issues occurring in the present. The "Futures Thinking Model" created a vision for where to head as a means to be more

reflective in strategic planning. It included determining through secondary sources (newspaper clippings, journals, articles) regarding current events or situations about the funeral industry, determining what might happen in the future and what would likely happen based on secondary sources and interviews with respondents, and determining through interviews with the respondents their plans or actions that they must carry out to address the perceived events in the future (foresight).

Conceptual and Analytical Framework

Financial Performance of Funeral Industry

The evaluation of competitiveness and sustainability of financial performance of funeral industry showed that management accounting techniques played an important function in creating a sustainable competitive advantage for funeral industry (Wadesango et al., 2021). The contribution of sustainable development was largely dependent on the business' perceptions of the advantages of sustainability and competitive strategies and consequent practices. The relationship between competitive performance and financial performance had been heavily debated with mixed results measuring the possible mediators in the sustainability-financial performance relationship (Cantele and Zardini, 2018).

Financial performance as to liquidity ratios, leverage, efficiency, and profitability measured funeral business' overall financial health. Liquidity ratio measured a funeral business ability to pay debt obligations and its margin of safety through the calculation of metrics including the current ratio, quick ratio, and operating cash flow ratio. Leverage ratio measured the level of debt incurred by a funeral business against several other accounts in its balance sheet, income statement, or cash flow statement. Efficiency ratio measured a funeral business' ability to use its assets to generate income, and profitability ratio assessed a funeral business' ability to earn profits from its sales or operations.

Financial performance was a measurement of how well the funeral industry could use its assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. It was also a general measure of the industry's overall financial health and condition over a given period. Determining the Industry's performance using a set of financial ratios had been interesting and challenging for many researchers and practitioners. Identification of factors that could accurately determine the factors affecting a good financial performance was of great interest to any decision maker (Delen et al., 2013).

External Factor

The social, economic, and formal practices dimensions of sustainability positively affected competitive advantage mediated by the business' reputation, customer satisfaction, and organizational commitment. The competitive advantage to be a mediator positively contributed to financial performance (Cantele and Zardini, 2018). In analyzing the external factors, Porter's Five Forces identified the competition, new entrants into the industry, supplier power, buyer power, and the threat of substitute

products and services in the market. Also, the PESTLE was an analytical tool that identified how various factors may affect an organization and its competitive standing.

Porter's five forces framework was based on the perception and understanding that a business strategy should encounter the opportunities and threats in the business' external setting. A competitive strategy should rest on an understanding of industry framework and the way they change. Porter argued that the aim of the strategist was to recognize, understand, and handle a competitive business environment by directly looking at competitors, or to contemplate a broader perspective that competed against the industry (Porter, 1979). Arguably, technological advancements and different ways of strategic thinking such as shaping the future or futures thinking, engaging with customers, and creating long-term value using innovative ways may have shifted Porter's five forces thinking from competing in an existing competitive business environment to seeking opportunities in new innovative markets. However, one may wonder, if business were up to par for stepping out of their current competitive market to become a pioneer in a new market environment (Bruijl, 2018).

As to competitive advantage, the use of relevant, authentic studies would provide information in the end result of this study, such as the study "Growth Drivers in Selected Death Care Businesses in the Philippines, 2020". This study determined the growth drivers of death care businesses in the Philippines and formulated alternative strategic management considering that the growth in the death care industry was fueled by various factors such as external factors. External factors consisted of Political Factors which focused on how government policy and actions intervened in the economy and other factors that could affect a business. Political factors involved the relationship between business and the government. Economic Factors took into account the various aspects of the economy and how the outlook on each area could impact the business. Economic indicators were usually measured and reported by Central Banks and other Government Agencies. Social Factors were related to the cultural and demographic trends of society. Social norms and pressures were key to determining consumer behavior. Technological Factors were linked to innovation in the industry as well as innovation in the overall economy. Not being up to date with the latest trends of a particular industry could be extremely harmful to operations. Environmental Factors concerned the ecological impacts on business. As weather extremes became more common, businesses need to plan how to adapt to these changes. Legal Factors pertained to any legal forces that define what a business could or could not do. Political and legal factors could intersect when governmental bodies introduced legislature and policies that affected how businesses operated (Feys, 2015).

Challenges of Funeral Industry

The challenges included handling human remains which required significant start-up capital. It was an environmentally sensitive business that must adhere to stringent national environmental health guidelines (Maphela, 2021). Since Death and funeral practices were a constant, funeral industry must participate in a diverse range of online

practices related to Sorry Business, including notifications of deaths and funerals, offering condolences and extending support, and grieving and healing (Carlson, 2015).

Challenges on businesses included external factors related to financial crisis and downturn in the market (Hunter, 2012). PESTLE analysis was utilized for the identification of the political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental factors that had positive or negative effect on the greatest environmental threats facing the globe today (Christodoulou, 2019).

Futures Thinking Model

Responding to the challenges, the “futures thinking” helped in the unprecedented global change, decreased difficulties in an environment of growing complexity, heightened uncertainty, and accelerated pace of change. It was essentially concerned with the future. The “futures thinking” model facilitated decision-making processes and outcomes that demonstrated sustainable thinking (Lederwasch, 2012).

Figure 1. Analytical Framework, Source: Inayatullah (2003)

Using the Generic Foresight Process (GFP) Framework, the output of the study was a proposed contextualized “Futures Thinking Model”. A generic foresight process framework recognized several distinct phases, from the initial gathering of information to the production of outputs intended as input into the more familiar activities of strategy development and strategic planning. The framework would be useful as a diagnostic tool

for examining how foresight work and strategy were undertaken, as well as a design aid for customized foresight projects and processes (Voros, 2003).

The Futures Thinking Model was crafted by adopting the required key elements from The Generic Foresight Process (GFP) Framework such as (1) Determining through secondary sources (newspaper clippings, journals, articles) regarding current events or situations about the funeral industry, (2) Determining what might happen in the future and what would likely happen based on secondary sources and interviews with respondents, (3) Determining through interviews with the respondents the plans or actions that they must carry out to address the perceived events in the future (foresight), and (4) Finally, coming up with a futures thinking model that summarized and integrated all these data drawn from secondary sources and interviews.

Figure 2. *Research Paradigm*

Reflected in the Research Paradigm was the profile characteristics of the funeral industry. Funeral industry was one of the oldest businesses in the market, considering it was usually a sole-proprietorship or family business. Business and its employees mutually coexisted and nurtured one another. Funeral business invested in and supported its employees as well as the local communities. This symbiotic relationship enabled the

funeral business and its owners and managers to work harmoniously. The funeral's capital was provided by the family who owned the business. They provided support systems as well (Sheth, 2020).

The funeral industry's financial performance was a subjective measure of how well the funeral industry can cope with the present situation including the use its assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. The key indicators drawn from the financial statements were liquidity which indicated the ability of the funeral business to meet its financial obligations when they come due; leverage ratio was a financial measurement that assessed the ability of the funeral business to meet its financial obligations. It was a measure of how much the funeral business used its equity and debt to finance its assets. Efficiency measured a funeral's ability to use its assets to generate income and measure the level of performance achieved against a standard. Profitability measured the income and expenses. Profitability was a situation in which a business generated a profit that relied heavily on the funeral services depending on their business plan, good business operation habits, connections with their clientele, satisfactory market, continuous improvement of management, and strategic and structured marketing tools that generated greater efficiency and income.

The growth in the funeral industry was fueled by external factors such as staying competitively to produce goods or services in a better or more affordable manner as compared to its rivals. The funeral industry being one of the oldest businesses in the market and considering individual funeral industries, may have established certain competitive advantage over the other rivals. The success of funeral industries was largely due to continued increasing demand at the rate of population growth. The Porter's Five Forces framework determined the competitive structure of a funeral industry and its profitability. The funeral business structure, and its relative position within the industry were the two basic drivers of industry's profitability. A PESTLE analysis was a tool used to gain a macro picture of a funeral industry environment. Considering that the funeral industry was in a market where there was competition, the creation and implementation of strategies were meant to survive (Hernandez, 2013).

The pandemic had challenged the funeral industry in unprecedented levels. Dealing with an increase in the number of deaths, having very strict guidelines had affected the industry's over-all operations. From its humble beginnings, the funeral industry had gained the recognition and excellence among their respective communities by providing recession-proof services thru test of time, and raised its level of competence in line with National standards of Funeral services.

To this end, the Futures Thinking Model for funeral industry was proposed.

Research Questions

This study sought to determine the financial performance of the Funeral Industry in Nueva Vizcaya as moderated by external factors towards competitive advantage. Specifically, it aimed to:

1. Describe the business profile characteristics of the Funeral Industry along the following:
 - 1.1. Type of Ownership
 - 1.2. Number of years in business
 - 1.3. Number of employees
 - 1.4. Capital at the end of each year
 - 1.5. Services Offered
 - 1.6. Marketing Platforms
 - 1.7. Linkages
2. Describe the Financial Performance of the Funeral Industry in the following key indicators:
 - 2.1. Liquidity
 - 2.2. Leverage
 - 2.3. Efficiency
 - 2.4. Profitability
3. Determine the factors of good financial performance of the Funeral Industry towards competitive advantage in terms of:
 - 3.1. The Porter's Five Forces
 - 3.2. The PESTLE
4. Determine the challenges encountered by the Funeral Industry along External factors.
5. Propose a "Futures Thinking Model" for the Funeral Industry in Nueva Vizcaya.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This employed the quantitative-qualitative approach, particularly the descriptive design of research. The main mode of gathering data in this study was the conduct of interviews where the researcher directed questions upon the informants. Data gathered were corroborated by information gathered from document-scanning particularly from documents requested from the informants which were the financial statements of each funeral homes business involved in this study over the past five years. The quantitative design, particularly the descriptive type was used in describing the profile characteristics of the funeral industry.

The qualitative design gave a deeper understanding and comprehensive analysis of determining the factors of good financial performance of the funeral industry towards

competitive advantages. The researcher used Porter's Five Forces, formed by Michael E. Porter in Harvard Business School. For the external Factors, Porter's Five Forces was used to recognize and analyze the different forces in the competitive environment, suppliers' bargaining power, buyers' bargaining power, threat of new entrants, threat of substitution, and the rivalry among competing firms which constituted a certain industry that determined its competitive advantage. Also, the researcher used the PESTLE framework. PESTLE analysis was an important and widely used tool that helped show the big picture of a firm's external environment. PESTLE is an acronym for the political, economic, sociocultural, technological, environmental, and legal contexts in which the funeral industry operated. The qualitative design for deeper understanding and analysis was also used for the challenges encountered by the funeral industry.

Research Locale

Legend: : Location of the involved Funeral Businesses in the Study.

Figure 3. Map of the Province of Nueva Vizcaya

The study was conducted within the province of Nueva Vizcaya consisting of 15 municipalities. Among these 15, the researcher conducted her study in the towns of Solano, Bayombong, Bambang, Bagabag, Aritao and Quezon where the funeral entrepreneur-informants were located. There were two funeral businesses in Solano, two in Bayombong, one in Bambang, one in Bagabag, two in Aritao, one in Quezon and one in Villaverde. The funeral business' respondents in these particular towns were identified from the list taken from the provincial office of the Department of Trade and Industry (See Appendix I). There were funeral industries in other towns. However, due to the COVID situation, strict travel protocols were a limitation on the part of the researcher. Thus, funeral industries from the above-mentioned towns were considered since these towns

were the ones nearer to the capital town of Bayombong and commercial center town of Solano where they were considered to be at the most active economic activities.

Table 1. *Research Respondents*

Funeral	Number of respondents	Respondents
A	1	Manager/Owner
B	1	Employee
C	2	Employees
D	1	Employee
E	1	Employee
F	1	Employee
G	1	Employee
H	1	Manager

Purposive sampling was the method used in the identification of research informants. Apart from the two owners or managers of the identified funeral industry businesses, seven key employees upon the referral of the owners or managers were also included. The list from the provincial office of the Department of Trade and Industry was the basis in the identification of the necessary informants. The researcher provided an Informed Consent Form and filled by the informants. It served as the consent of his or her willingness to participate in the conduct of the study.

Research Instruments

In determining the business profile characteristics of the funeral industry, an interview guide was used. The interview guide was validated by the experts and certified to be compliant with the University Research Ethics Board (UREB).

The foremost research instrument utilized in this study was the financial statements over the last five years of the identified Funeral Industry. The Profitability Ratios were determined upon scrutiny on the financial statements. Thus, an analysis of the Five Year Comprehensive Financial Statement was requested, and an Interview guide was used as a complementary research instrument that triangulated the findings (See Appendix E).

In determining the factors affecting good financial performance of funeral industry towards competitive advantage, Porter's Five Forces framework was used as a strategic analytical tool to assess and evaluate the level of intensity of competition in the funeral industry. Also, the PESTLE analysis was used to analyze and monitor the macro-environmental (external marketing environment) factors that had an impact on the Funeral Industry.

In determining the challenges encountered by the funeral industry, the researcher directed questions upon the informants with the use of the interview guide.

In the contextualization of the Futures thinking model for the funeral industry in Nueva Vizcaya, the researcher also used the interview guide.

Data Gathering Procedure

In collecting data from the informants, the researcher sought their consent via a letter-request to conduct the study. The informants also were the ones who set the interview date and time. With the risk of COVID-19, the researcher strictly followed the mandated safety protocols of the municipalities where the business was situated. The wearing of face mask and maintaining physical distancing were maintained during a series of interviews. The researcher used an interview guide question in conducting face-to-face interview with the funeral services owners. A documentary analysis was also used in this study. In case of clarifications and additional queries, the researcher was allowed to call or text the informants for a follow-up interview.

Treatment of Data / Data Analyses

For the profile, qualitative analysis was used. After the interviews with the informants, the data gathered were transcribed and analyzed. The requested financial statements for five years were scanned, utilized, reviewed, and relevant figures therein were used in computing for the businesses' liquidity, leverage, efficiency, and profitability with the corresponding formula as presented below:

Table 2. Financial Performance Key Indicators

Liquidity	$\text{Current ratio} = \frac{\text{Current assets}}{\text{Current liabilities}}$ $\text{Quick ratio} = \frac{(\text{Current Assets} - \text{Inventories} - \text{Prepaid Expenses})}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$ $\text{Cash ratio} = \frac{(\text{Cash} + \text{Marketable Securities})}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$
Leverage	$\text{Debt-to-equity ratio} = \frac{\text{Total liabilities}}{\text{Total shareholders' equity}}$ $\text{Debt-to-asset ratio} = \frac{\text{Total debt}}{\text{Total assets}}$
Efficiency	$\text{Asset turnover ratio} = \frac{\text{Net sales or revenue}}{\text{average total assets}}$
Profitability	$\text{Net Profit margin rate} = \frac{(\text{Total Revenue} - \text{Total Expenses})}{\text{Total Revenue}}$ $\text{Gross Profit rate} = \frac{\text{Gross profit}}{\text{Net sales}}$ $\text{ROA} = \frac{\text{Net profit}}{\text{Total average assets}}$ $\text{ROE} = \frac{\text{Net profit}}{\text{Shareholders' equity}}$

A qualitative analysis was used to determine the factors of good financial performance of the funeral industry towards competitive advantage. The researcher analyzed data gathered and used the framework known as Porter's Five Forces analysis and PESTLE. Data gathered from the challenges encountered and Futures thinking model by the funeral industry were analyzed and transcribed.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Section 1. Business profile characteristics of the Funeral Industry

This section discusses the relevant business profile characteristics of the funeral businesses involved in this study. Particularly, these profile characteristics were the Type of Ownership, Number of Years in business, Number of employees, Capitalization, Services Offered, Marketing Platforms, and Linkages.

Table 3. *Profile Characteristics of the Funeral Industry in terms of Type of Ownership, Year established, Number of years in Business, and Number of employees*

Funeral	Type of Ownership	Year established	Number of Years in business	Number of employees
A	Single Proprietorship	1999	23 yrs.	5
B	Single Proprietorship	2006	16 yrs.	5
C	Single Proprietorship	1985	37 yrs.	5
D	Single Proprietorship	1976	46 yrs.	5
E	Single Proprietorship	2006	16 yrs.	5
F	Partnership	1945	77 yrs.	6
G	Single Proprietorship	2007	15 yrs.	3
H	Corporation	2007	13 yrs.	4

Among the eight Funeral businesses, there were six Single Proprietorship, one Partnership, and one Corporation type of ownership. Funerals A, C, and D were second generation proprietorship that were transferred after the death of the previous owners. Funerals B, E, and G were established by the current proprietors who learned the business through their experiences as past workers in Funeral homes. Funeral F was established as a single Proprietorship but after the death of the previous owner, the funeral business was transferred to his children and became a partnership among his children. Funeral H was founded in the 1970s, and the company claimed to cover about 95 percent of the market share in pre-need plans. It currently had the widest network of branches in the industry, with around 290 memorial chapels and around 300 Life Plan offices (www.stpeter.com).

The oldest from the funeral industry was established in 1945, and the recent was established in 2007. Four from the industry ranged from 13-20 years, and the other four ranged from 21-77 years in the business.

From among the respondents, two funeral businesses had at least three employees, and six employed at least five employees composed of a Licensed embalmer who was usually the owner, one or two assistants or helpers, and a driver.

Table 4. Profile in Terms of Capitalization of the Funeral Industry

Funeral Industry	Initial Capital (in thousand Pesos)	% of Change of Capital 2017 vs. Initial Capital	Ending Capital 2017 (in thousand Pesos)	% of Change in Capital 2018 vs. 2017	Ending Capital 2018 (in thousand Pesos)	% of Change of Capital 2019 vs. 2018	Ending Capital 2019 (in thousand Pesos)	% of Change of Capital 2020 vs. 2019	Ending Capital 2020 (in thousand Pesos)	% of Change of Capital 2021 vs. 2019	Ending Capital 2021 (in thousand Pesos)
A	800	719	6,552	3	6,766	4	7,026	8	7,575	10	8,354
B	1,200	252	4,226	3	4,333	5	4,549	17	5,313	7	5,698
C	100	2,387	2,486	39	3,451	18	4,074	16	4,725	15	5,414
D	30	10,101	3,060	15	3,531	3	3,624	3	3,749	0	3,732
E	1,000	132	2,324	27	2,951	7	3,155	2	3,208	-1	3,189
F	5	73,875	3,698	4	3,834	4	3,979	5	4,162	4	4,316
G	1,000	114	2,141	5	2,254	60	3,598	-16	3,021	17	3,548
H	2,000	97	3,940	11	4,386	11	4,874	11	5,412	11	6,006

The initial capitalization of the funeral businesses tremendously grew from the year of establishment up to the end of 2021 considering the number of years in business and factors like steady demand in the funeral services offered, good financial performance business management, and competitiveness. It could be inferred that the increase in the capitalization was due to the presence of strong linkages that could promote service efficiency, productivity, increase economic opportunity, technological and managerial capabilities, and market diversification in the funeral industry which eventually resulted to their profitability.

The Initial capitalization of the funeral businesses ranged from Php 5,000- Php 2,000,000 depending on the year the business was established. There was an increasing pattern of capitalization on the last five years because they were generating profit or income which meant that the generated income were rolled-over as additional working capital for the following years.

Table 5. *Profile in Terms of Services Offered by the Funeral Industries in terms of Primary Services, Secondary Services, Marketing Platforms and Linkages*

Funeral	Services (Primary)	Services (Secondary)	Marketing Platforms	Linkages
A	embalming to burial	Flowers and tombstone	Facebook Page, Word-of-mouth, Signage and Personal Selling	Suppliers of coffins, medicines, flowers, tombstone, printing press, and cemeteries
B		Flowers and tombstone		
C		Flowers and tombstone		
D		Flowers and tombstone		
E		Flowers		
F		Flowers and tombstone		
G		Flowers and tombstone		
H		Flowers		

The table presents the profile of the funeral industry in terms of services, marketing platforms and linkages. It can be gleaned from the table that all funeral businesses in the province Nueva Vizcaya had a primary and standard service of embalming to burial that include removal of cadaver at its place of death, bringing the cadaver to the morgue for sanitation and embalming procedures, grooming, and sealing in a coffin, delivery to the place of burial whether at the home of the bereaved family or at the chapel of the service provider, processing of necessary permits, and funeral coach in time of interment.

Most of the funeral businesses provided secondary services that included flowers, flower arrangements and tombstone and others like video coverage, pictorials, provision of “Thank You” cards, and balloons were provided upon the request of the bereaved family with additional service charges exclusive of the funeral package, except for Funerals E and F.

Marketing Platforms

In terms of marketing platforms used, all funeral businesses used Facebook Page, word-of-mouth, signage and personal selling. They utilized marketing platforms because if the customer was satisfied, they would definitely recommend to their family and friends (Sari et al., 2018). However, most of the Funeral Industry’s FB page were not updated. Facebook business pages were excellent platforms to gather their customers, provide reviews, share opinions, voice concerns, and offer feedback. They could build a community on their Facebook page in a number of ways, including posting useful, relevant, and interesting links. Having strong marketing strategies could increase revenue because these platforms built customer awareness and opportunities for feedback for a better service. The Word-of-mouth essentially was a free advertising tool triggered by customer experiences. It is about the customers’ sharing of their thoughts about the funeral services thereby indirectly encouraging more sales and recommendations for the funeral industry like a ripple effect. Funeral industry signage was used as a versatile marketing tool to boost their brand value, draw new customers, and increase revenue/profit. Personal selling was an important marketing tool for the funeral industry that sold complex or high-value services to customers. Their respective employees dealt

with individual customers who inquired face-to-face or thru phone. Samples of their marketing ads included “Nawa’y Bawat Pamilya May ST.PETER Life Plan”, “The Largest Servicing Mortuary in Cagayan Valley”, and “The First Funeral Home in Nueva Vizcaya”.

Funeral industries competed through marketing such as competitiveness and building a good reputation as being reliable (Halpenny, 2013).

Linkages

In terms of linkages, all funeral businesses had existing linkages that did not require MOA or MOU with hospitals, the Philippine National Police (PNP), and the Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (MDRRMO). They also had linkages with insurance companies but were not updated. All funeral businesses mentioned, except for Funeral C which was identified as accredited, that they were authorized to cater to COVID-positive cadavers for the Municipality of Solano, and Funeral D for the Municipality of Bayombong. All the funeral Industry key informants shared that they had strong and harmonious working ties with their respective suppliers of coffin, medicines, flower shops, tombstone suppliers, and printing services providers. A vital aspect of building and maintaining a successful funeral industry was cultivating strong connections with their respective local communities because being present and active in the community built trust, business recognition, and that gave the funeral industry purpose and credibility.

Literature on peacebuilding emphasized the need for partnership and linkages at all levels of business for sustainability. Thus, “Networking” was an important factor for the success of entrepreneurs and their businesses (Yoosuf and Premarante, 2017).

Section 2. Financial Performance of the Funeral Industry in the following key indicators: Liquidity, Leverage, Efficiency and Profitability

This section discusses the financial performance of the funeral industry and their general well-being. These are snapshot of their financial health and provide insight into the future, whether its operations and profits are on track towards growth and competitiveness.

2.1 LIQUIDITY

Liquidity ratios per Funeral

Liquidity ratios measured a business’ ability to pay debt obligations and its margin of safety through the calculation of metrics including the current ratio, quick ratio, and operating cash flow ratio. An industry’s standard liquidity ratio higher than 1 was a “good” liquidity ratio which means that the business is worthy of investment. Results showed that the funeral businesses had increasing liquidity ratios. These ratios showed the relationship of the business’ current assets to its current liabilities (Aduana, 2015). Liabilities were classified as short-term or current obligations when they were expected

to be settled within 12 months after the date of the statement of financial position. The factors that contributed to the liquidity of funeral industry were the number of years of good financial performance and their ability to raise cash when needed. There were two major determinants of a funeral industry's liquidity position. The first was its ability to convert assets to cash to pay its current liabilities (short-term liquidity). The second was its debt capacity. Current liabilities, on the other hand, were obligations due within a year (Aduana, 2015). It was important to keep a reasonable ratio of current assets to current liabilities to ensure that short-term obligations can be paid on time, opportunities for volume expansion can be seized, and unforeseen circumstances could be handled easily. If a funeral business had a current ratio of more than one, then it was a good indicator that it could cover its current liabilities on time. Outside creditors would consider this a positive data to finance this company whenever a need of loan arises.

Table 6 shows the current ratio of the respondent-funeral industries:

Current Ratio

Table 6. *Current Ratio of the Funeral Industry*

CURRENT RATIO					
RESPONDENTS	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
A	2.05	2.85	4.24	8.60	23.99
B	2.53	2.14	1.91	2.73	4.00
C	-	2.40	5.34	10.37	27.84
D	-	-	-	-	-
E	1.73	5.15	10.73	21.54	-
F	-	-	3.66	8.02	-
G	-	1.78	4.30	10.20	29.93
H	0.54	1.12	1.97	3.79	9.53

Funeral A

As shown in the table, a closer look at the funeral A's current ratio per year revealed that there was a significant increase in the company's current ratio for the years 2020 and 2021. In 2020, the current ratio doubled from 4.24 in 2019 to 8.60. For 2021, on the other hand, the current ratio nearly tripled from 8.60 in 2020 to 23.99. The funeral was very liquid thus, the decreasing total current liability per year resulted to Funeral A's increasing current ratio per year. Funeral A's financial statements indicated that there was a consistent increase in the current ratio per year from 2.05 in 2017 to 23.99 in 2021. This

showed that Funeral A had maintained more than sufficient current assets every year to meet its currently maturing obligations. However, one may surmise that Funeral A was not efficiently using its current assets or was not utilizing the benefits of short-term financing due to idle cash.

Funeral B

The same table also shows that Funeral B, for the past five years, had remained above the general rule of thumb of 2:1. While the business' current ratio experienced a slight dip in 2019 with a current ratio of 1.91 for that year, the current ratio was able to bounce back to 2.73 in 2020. Overall, the funeral's current ratio was stable as it was able to maintain sufficient current assets to meet its current liabilities. The current assets which were inventories were easily converted into cash in terms of sales.

Funeral C

In like manner, Funeral C's current ratios per year would reveal that the current ratio doubled every year. Generally, having a cash ratio above 1 was recommended in case of unlikely event that the other non-cash current assets proved difficult to liquidate. The consistent increase per year in the funeral's current ratio may be the result of two factors: (a) the consistent increase in the company's net income per year thereby increasing assets in general; and (b) the consistent decreasing balance of the business' current liabilities per year.

Funeral D

The data gathered for Funeral D showed that all the cash realized from operations and all the merchandise inventory of the company were available as Funeral D's working capital. As such was the case, the business' current ratios could not be computed because the company did not have any reported liabilities for the past five years. Having zero liabilities did not necessarily mean a good thing as Funeral D may be sacrificing the potential utilization of resources that was debt-generated. Furthermore, the tax shield benefit of interest expense was forgone.

Funeral E

Similarly, the table also shows that Funeral E's current ratio increased dramatically per year with 1.73 for 2017 as the lowest and 21.54 for 2020 as the highest. Moreover, the current ratio for 2021 could not be computed because the company did not have any current liability for this period. The consistent and significant increase in the current ratios per year was consistent with the significant increase in the cash balance per year coupled with a decrease in the Accounts Payable balance reported per year. Worth noting was the fact that the current ratio increased in 2020 to 21.54 from 10.73 in 2019 despite the business experiencing a significant decline in its net income for 2020 which also resulted to a slight decrease in its cash balance for 2020.

Funeral F

An analysis of Funeral F's financial statements showed that it was only in the years 2019 and 2020 that the business reported a liability. It indicated that, for the years 2017, 2018, and 2021, the company's current ratio could not be computed because the company did not have any reported liability for those periods. However, for the years 2019 and 2020, the company's current ratio was 3.66 and 8.02, respectively.

Funeral G

For the past five years, the current ratios of Funeral G were 1.78 in 2018 as the lowest and 29.93 in 2021 as the highest. The table also showed that the business' current ratio for the first three years was below the general rule of thumb of 2:1.

The significant increase in the current ratio for the years 2020 and 2021 could be explained by the significant increase in the business' total cash for the years mentioned owing to the increase in net income for the same period. Another reason why the funeral's current ratio experienced a steady increase in the past five years was the fact that the funeral's current liabilities, specifically accounts payable, were decreasing per year.

Funeral H

Similarly, Funeral H experienced a significant increase in the current ratio for the years 2020 and 2021 which could be explained by the significant increase in the business' total cash for the years mentioned owing to the increase in net income for the same period. Another reason why the funeral's current ratio had a steady increase in the past five years was the fact that the funeral's current liabilities, specifically accounts payable, were decreasing per year.

Cash Ratio

It can be surmised that the similarities in the increasing trend of the current and cash ratios per year could be due to the fact that the business' current assets consisted mainly of cash and inventories. In addition, the funeral industry did not experience significant changes in the inventory balance per year. Table 7 shows the cash ratio of each respondent-funeral industry.

Table 7. *Cash Ratio of the Funeral Industry*

CASH RATIO					
RESPONDENTS	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
A	0.38	0.51	0.74	2.73	10.85
B	0.15	0.25	0.51	1.32	1.88
C	-	1.67	4.26	8.55	23.76
D	-	-	-	-	-
E	0.43	3.21	7.47	14.25	-
F	-	-	1.91	4.08	-
G	-	0.61	2.57	7.28	23.40
H	0.08	0.46	0.99	2.15	5.86

As what had been observed in other funeral industry-respondents of this study, the similarities in the increasing trend of the current and cash ratios per year could be explained by the fact that the company's current assets consisted mainly of cash and inventories and that the company did not experience significant increase or decrease in its inventory balance per year.

Funeral A

As to Funeral A's cash ratio, the same increasing trend per year for the current ratio for the past five years could be observed with the company experiencing significant increases for the years 2020 and 2021. In 2020, the cash ratio jumped from 0.74 in 2019 to 2.73. For 2021, on the other hand, the quick ratio moved from 2.73 in 2020 to 10.85.

As shown in the table, Funeral A, since in the computation of cash ratio, inventory balance which remained relatively stable was simply eliminated, the resulting cash ratio per period necessarily would mirror the business' current ratio which was significantly influenced by the cash balance per year.

Funeral B

As to Funeral B's cash ratio, an increasing trend per year for the past five years could be observed too, with the company experiencing significant increases for the years 2019, 2020, and 2021. The cash ratios for these periods were 0.51, 1.32, and 1.88. It was worthy to note at this point that, for the first three years (2017 – 2019), the business' cash ratios were below 1 despite having current ratios above 2:1 for the same periods.

Generally, having a cash ratio above 1 was recommended in case of unlikely event that the other non-cash current assets proved difficult to liquidate. For Funeral B, this meant that for the years mentioned, most of the business' current assets were tied up to its merchandise inventory. It was only in the years 2019 and 2020 that the business was able to have a cash ratio of at least 1.

Funeral C

The table also showed that Funeral C's cash ratio followed the same increasing trend as that of the current ratios per year. In other words, the business' cash ratio also doubled per year, or even higher. The increasing trend of the cash ratios per year could be explained by the fact that the business' current assets consisted mainly of cash and inventories and that the business did not experience a significant increase or decrease in its inventory balance per year.

Funeral D

Just like the business' current ratios, the cash ratios could not be computed because the company did not have any reported liabilities for the past five years. Again, having zero liabilities was not necessarily a good thing because it may mean that Funeral D would be sacrificing the potential utilization of resources that were debt-generated. Furthermore, the tax shield benefit of interest expense was forgone. Moreover, it could mean that all the cash realized from operations and all the merchandise inventory of the company were available as Funeral D's working capital.

Funeral E

The sudden spike in current and cash ratio of Funeral E suggested low debt utilization as with the case of Funeral A. Funeral E's cash ratio per period mirrored the business' increasing current ratio per year with 0.43 in 2017 as the lowest and 14.25 in 2020 as the highest.

A significant increase per year in the business' cash ratio was evident. The trend was a result of the significant increase in the business' cash balance per year coupled with a uniform reduction in the balance of the business' current liabilities per year.

Funeral F

As to Funeral F, the cash ratios for the years 2017, 2018, and 2021 could not be computed because the business did not have any reported liability for those periods.

For the years 2019 and 2020, the business' cash ratios were 1.91 and 4.08, respectively. It could be observed that the business' cash ratios for 2019 and 2020 were almost half of its current ratio. This meant that the company's total current assets were distributed almost evenly to cash and merchandise inventory.

Funeral G

The movement in Funeral G's cash ratio per period was largely influenced by the significant increase in the cash balance per year considering that the business' current assets consisted mainly of cash and inventories. The increasing cash ratio per year of Funeral G was parallel to the business' increasing current ratio per year. The cash ratio was at its lowest at 0.61 in 2018 and at its highest at 23.40 in 2021. The movement in Funeral G's cash ratio per period was largely influenced by the significant increase in the cash balance per year considering that the company's current assets which consisted mainly of cash and inventories did not experience a significant increase or decrease in its inventory balance per year.

Funeral H

The cash ratio per year of Funeral H was parallel to the business' increasing current ratio per year. For the first three years, the cash ratio fell below 1 with 0.08 for 2017, 0.46 for 2018, and 0.99 for 2019. This meant that for those years, the business did not have enough cash to settle its liabilities assuming they fell due. For 2020 and 2021, however, the business was able to increase its cash ratio to 2.15 and 5.86, respectively which indicated that enough cash was available to settle currently maturing obligations. However, this also meant that for those periods, a bulk of the business' current assets were tied up to its inventory.

Table 8. *Summary Table of Liquidity Ratios of the Funeral Industry*

Funeral	2017		2018		2019		2020		2021	
	Current Ratio	Cash Ratio								
A	2.05	0.38	2.85	0.51	4.24	0.74	8.60	2.73	23.99	10.85
B	2.53	0.15	2.14	0.25	1.91	0.51	2.73	1.32	4.00	1.88
C	-	-	2.40	1.67	5.34	4.26	10.37	8.55	27.84	23.76
D	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
E	1.73	0.43	5.15	3.21	10.73	7.47	21.54	14.25	-	-
F	-	-	-	-	3.66	1.91	8.02	4.08	-	-
G	-	-	1.78	0.61	4.30	2.57	10.20	7.28	29.93	23.40
H	0.54	0.08	1.12	0.46	1.97	0.99	3.79	2.15	9.53	5.86

The funeral industry used cash basis to record income and expenses as received and incurred, respectively. Revenues were recognized only upon collection while payables were recorded upon payment. This was the reason why the funeral businesses did not have current liability. Cash basis accounting was advantageous to them because

it was simpler and less expensive than accrual accounting. Also, it gave an accurate picture of how much cash was on hand. They had sufficient and stable cash flow, as no current liabilities were recorded. A non-current liability referred to the financial obligations in a funeral industry's balance sheet that were not expected to be paid within one year. The appropriate magnitude for this ratio varied widely among industries, companies, and the specific circumstances of individual companies. However, a popular rule of thumb was that a company's current ratio should be at least 2 is to 1.

There were two main liquidity ratios used. These were the current ratio and cash ratio. The cash ratio represented the extent to which the funeral industry can pay its short-term obligations with its most liquid assets. In other words, it measured the proportion of a business' current liabilities that it could meet with cash and assets that could be readily converted to cash. All the funeral industries were liquid and could pay their current obligations.

Furthermore, the cash ratio was a liquidity measure that showed a funeral industry's ability to cover its short-term obligations using only cash and cash equivalents. Funeral D had zero Cash ratio because it had no short-term obligations. Funeral E and F had zero Cash ratio for the year 2021 because they had fully-paid all their short-term obligations. All funeral industries in the last five years measured greater than one cash ratio which was considered a high cash ratio. It indicated that a funeral industry had more than enough cash to cover the short-term debts on its balance sheet. For the two accredited funeral businesses which catered to COVID-positive cadavers, they had an increase of their current and cash ratios. While from an owner's perspective this might seem favorable, the current ratio should not be too high. As mentioned earlier, having a too high liquidity ratios might mean that the resources of the funerals were being sidelined when the cash on hand could be used to expand operations or improve equipment.

Overall, the similarities in the increasing trend of the current and cash ratios per year could be explained by the fact that the business' current assets consisted mainly of cash and inventories and that the businesses did not experience significant increase or decrease in its inventory balance per year. It is then safe to say that the funeral industry was very liquid as shown by their high current and cash ratios.

The consistent increase per year in the funeral's current ratio may be the result of two factors: (a) the consistent increase in the company's net income per year thereby increasing assets in general; and (b) the consistent decreasing balance of the company's current liabilities per year.

The similarities in the increasing trend of the current and cash ratios per year could be explained by the fact that the business' current assets consisted mainly of cash and inventories and that the company did not experience significant increase or decrease in its inventory balance per year while the cash balance consistently increased per year. Given the fact that liabilities continued to be lowered every year, it was suggested that cash was either retained by the business or used for minimal operating expenditures.

2.1.2 Leverage Ratios of Funeral Industry

Debt to Equity Ratio

Table 9. *Debt to Equity Ratio of the Funeral Industry*

DEBT TO EQUITY RATIO					
RESPONDENTS	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
A	0.07	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.01
B	0.05	0.07	0.09	0.09	0.07
C	-	0.12	0.07	0.04	0.02
D	-	-	-	-	-
E	0.08	0.05	0.03	0.02	-
F	-	-	0.07	0.03	-
G	-	0.08	0.05	0.03	0.01
H	0.20	0.15	0.11	0.07	0.03

The Debt-to-Equity ratio indicated the proportion of debt in relation to resources provided by the owner. All the funeral industries had less than .02 which meant that they did not need additional financing from outside creditors. The ratios were generally considered good.

Debt to Asset Ratio

Table 10. *Debt to Asset Ratio of the Funeral Industry*

DEBT TO ASSETS RATIO					
RESPONDENTS	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
A	0.08	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.01
B	0.05	0.07	0.10	0.10	0.07
C	-	0.12	0.08	0.04	0.02
D	-	-	-	-	-
E	0.09	0.05	0.03	0.01	-
F	-	-	0.07	0.03	-
G	-	0.09	0.06	0.03	0.01
H	0.25	0.15	0.11	0.07	0.03

The table shows that all funeral businesses had very low debt-to-assets ratios which indicated that the industry exceeded their total amount of debts. Therefore, the industries enjoyed more financial flexibility which could be a factor to expand more aggressively since they did not need to spend a lot of money paying down debts. Also, the funeral industry such as Funeral H had a 'strong' leverage on market. On the other hand, if the debt-to-equity and debt-to-assets ratio were seen as too low, it might be a sign that the funerals relied too much on equity to finance the business positioning (Borres, 2020).

Table 11. *Summary Table of Leverage Ratios of the Funeral Industry*

Fun	2017		2018		2019		2020		2021	
	DER	DAR								
A	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.01
B	0.05	0.05	0.07	0.07	0.09	0.10	0.09	0.10	0.07	0.07
C	-	-	0.12	0.12	0.07	0.08	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02
D	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
E	0.08	0.09	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.01	-	-
F	-	-	-	-	0.07	0.07	0.03	0.03	-	-
G	-	-	0.08	0.09	0.05	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.01

H	0.20	0.25	0.15	0.15	0.11	0.11	0.07	0.07	0.03	0.03
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Legend: Fun- Funeral, DER- Debt to Equity Ratio, DAR- Debt to Assets ratio

The leverage ratios were financial measurements that assessed the ability of a funeral business to meet its financial obligations. It may also be used to measure a funeral's mix of operating expenses to get an idea of how changes in output would affect operating income (Aduana, 2015). The Leverage ratios used was Debt-to-Equity and Debt-to-Assets.

As shown table 11, there was a decrease of liabilities which meant that all funeral businesses had the capability to pay their short and long-term liabilities. It should be noted that while becoming more financially flexible due to having low-to-zero liabilities might be seen as a positive sign, each funeral business must assess its capital structures to determine the optimal mix of its sources of capital. It was undeniable that during times of uncertainties such as the COVID-19 pandemic, financial flexibility was highly valued. Each funeral business must still ensure that its assets were utilized and not remain idle. The forgone benefits of proper resource utilization might outweigh the cost of debt.

2.1.3 Efficiency Ratio

The efficiency ratios of the funeral businesses measured how well the funeral industries were managing their assets.

Asset Turnover Ratio

Table 12. *Asset Turnover Ratio of the Funeral Industry*

RESPONDENTS	ASSET TURNOVER RATIO				
	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
A	0.40	0.49	0.52	0.54	0.55
B	0.55	0.61	0.63	0.59	0.56
C	0.41	0.41	0.39	0.37	0.36
D	0.71	0.77	0.64	0.72	0.68
E	0.41	0.44	0.41	0.23	0.19
F	0.51	0.54	0.55	0.39	0.35
G	0.44	0.46	0.45	0.46	0.48
H	0.43	0.47	0.50	0.53	0.56

Table 12 shows whether the funeral industries had enough capital efficiently working by comparing their assets to sales. The asset turnover ratio was generally used to determine the efficiency of the business in using its resources/assets to generate sales.

As shown in Table 12, Funerals A and H consistently improved their efficiency in generating revenue for a period of five years although the other funerals had all shown assets turnover ranging from 0.19:1 to 0.68:1 particularly in 2021. The results of the Asset Turnover ratio was considered as a 'good' total turnover asset for the funeral industry as the total assets were able to produce enough revenue at the end of the year. However, due to the negative impact of the pandemic, Funerals E and F declined in their sales which also caused the decline of their asset turnover ratio.

If, compared to the entire industry, the funeral businesses had low asset turnover ratio, it might be an indicator that the assets were not utilized efficiently to generate sales. It might also be due to the utilization of cash to expand the operations or improve existing long-term assets that could improve operations.

2.1.4 Profitability Ratios

Net Profit Margin Rate

The Net Profit Margin Rate measured profitability of the funeral business and results of operations as a whole. The higher the better. The ratio represented the amount earned by the owners for each peso of sales.

Table 13. *Net Profit Margin Rate of the Funeral Industry*

NET PROFIT MARGIN RATE					
RESPONDENTS	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
A	0.18	0.21	0.20	0.26	0.29
B	0.09	0.12	0.16	0.16	0.12
C	0.27	0.31	0.36	0.40	0.43
D	0.16	0.18	0.13	0.14	0.10
E	0.29	0.40	0.40	0.20	0.05
F	0.20	0.16	0.16	0.05	0.14
G	0.09	0.15	0.21	0.27	0.33
H	0.11	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.12

As can be gleaned from Table 13, the funeral industry was a profitable business. The net profit rate ranged from 5% to 43%. Despite the pandemic wherein most funeral services were not availed, the linkage between the funeral industry, health care

institutions, and the government proved to be beneficial to the funeral industry, as revealed by the respondents during the interviews conducted with them.

Gross Profit Rate

The Gross Profit Margin Rate measured the reasonability of the price of the services of each funeral. Generally, the higher GPR, the better. But too high might mean the services or products were overpriced in order to accommodate their operating expenses.

Table 14. *Gross Profit Rate of the Funeral Industry*

GROSS PROFIT RATE					
RESPONDENTS	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
A	39.89	40.81	39.37	43.06	45.84
B	28.62	28.86	31.23	31.88	27.15
C	47.23	51.12	55.60	59.23	62.13
D	36.46	35.98	32.58	31.74	29.02
E	49.79	58.26	58.34	52.61	49.81
F	38.96	35.22	33.61	30.27	41.64
G	30.36	34.28	39.04	44.09	48.37
H	30.17	28.78	28.94	29.09	29.25

Based on table 14, the GPR of the funeral industry ranged from 28.62 to 62.13 which implies that the funeral industry is a very lucrative business despite its morbid nature.

Return on Assets Ratio

Return on Assets measured the amount earned by the owners for each peso of asset of the funeral business. Generally, the higher, the better. Too low ROA might be due to inefficient utilization of assets or might be an indicator that some assets needed replacing.

Table 15. *Return on Assets Ratio of the Funeral Industry*

RETURN ON ASSETS RATIO					
RESPONDENTS	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
A	0.07	0.10	0.10	0.13	0.15
B	0.05	0.07	0.09	0.09	0.07
C	0.11	0.12	0.13	0.14	0.15
D	0.12	0.13	0.08	0.10	0.07
E	0.12	0.16	0.15	0.05	0.01
F	0.10	0.09	0.08	0.02	0.05
G	0.04	0.06	0.09	0.12	0.15
H	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.06	0.06

The funeral industry registered a return on assets ratio ranging from 0.02 for F in 2020 to 0.16 for E in 2018. Funerals A, C, and G had consistently increased in their ROA while all the rest experienced an erratic trend in this said ratio.

Return on Equity

Return on Equity measured the amount earned by the owners for each peso of their invested value.

Table 16. *Return on Equity Ratio of the Funeral Industry*

RETURN ON EQUITY RATIOS					
RESPONDENTS	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
A	0.08	0.11	0.11	0.14	0.15
B	0.05	0.07	0.10	0.10	0.07
C	0.11	0.13	0.14	0.14	0.15
D	0.12	0.13	0.08	0.10	0.07
E	0.13	0.17	0.16	0.05	0.01
F	0.10	0.09	0.09	0.02	0.05
G	0.04	0.07	0.09	0.12	0.15
H	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.07

It was observed that the ROE of the funeral industry was relatively low despite the fact that almost all of them were equity financed due to low liabilities.

Summary of Profitability Measures

Overall, it can be stated that there was a good Profit Margin ratio. It was desirable since it meant the funeral industry generated more profits from its sales. The Gross Profit Rates were healthy which meant that the funeral industry did well in managing its cost of sales. It also showed that the business had more to cover for operating, financing, and other costs.

Table 17. *Summary Table of Profitability Ratios*

Fun	2017				2018				2019				2020				2021			
	NPMR	GPR	ROA	ROE																
A	0.18	39.89	0.07	0.08	0.21	40.81	0.10	0.11	0.20	39.37	0.10	0.11	0.26	43.06	0.13	0.14	0.29	45.84	0.15	0.15
B	0.09	28.62	0.05	0.05	0.12	28.86	0.07	0.07	0.16	31.23	0.09	0.10	0.16	31.88	0.09	0.10	0.12	27.15	0.07	0.07
C	0.27	47.23	0.11	0.11	0.31	51.12	0.12	0.13	0.36	55.60	0.13	0.14	0.40	59.23	0.14	0.14	0.43	62.13	0.15	0.15
D	0.16	36.46	0.12	0.12	0.18	35.98	0.13	0.13	0.13	32.58	0.08	0.08	0.14	31.74	0.10	0.10	0.10	29.02	0.07	0.07
E	0.29	49.79	0.12	0.13	0.40	58.26	0.16	0.17	0.40	58.34	0.15	0.16	0.20	52.61	0.05	0.05	0.05	49.81	0.01	0.01
F	0.20	38.96	0.10	0.10	0.16	35.22	0.09	0.09	0.16	33.61	0.08	0.09	0.05	30.27	0.02	0.02	0.14	41.64	0.05	0.05
G	0.09	30.36	0.04	0.04	0.15	34.28	0.06	0.07	0.21	39.04	0.09	0.09	0.27	44.09	0.12	0.12	0.33	48.37	0.15	0.15
H	0.11	30.17	0.05	0.06	0.10	28.78	0.05	0.06	0.11	28.94	0.05	0.06	0.11	29.09	0.06	0.06	0.12	29.25	0.06	0.07

Legend: Fun- Funeral, NPMR- Net Profit Margin Rate, GPR- Gross Profit Rate, ROA- Return on Assets, ROE- Return on Equity

The Return on Assets (ROA) results indicated that the funeral industry was able to maximize the use of its assets for getting more profits. The Return on Equity (ROE) result indicated that the funeral industry was more effective at generating profit from its existing assets. Likewise, the business which increased in its ROE over time was likely getting more efficient.

Profitability ratios were ratios that reflected the combined effects of liquidity and management in handling the assets and liabilities on the operating results of the funeral business. The ratios showed the effectiveness of business operations. (Aduana, 2015).

As an indicator of efficiency, there must be profit. Profit was a financial gain. It was the earnings from sales or revenue after deduction of all costs including interest payment on debt and tax (Bashar and Islam, 2014). Therefore, a high profit was an indication that a business was efficiently and effectively utilizing its funds (Aparna, 2015). Due to market liberalization, a business' ability to increase its profit, to survive and be competitive was more of an issue nowadays (Yazdanfar, 2013). There was a statistically significant positive relationship between profitability, liquidity, and firm size (Prempeh et al., 2018).

As shown in the Table 17, Funeral B, D, and E declined because Funeral B and E were non-accredited funeral industry to cater to COVID-positive cadavers. Funeral D's decline was due to the transition of new management because of the death of the previous owner. Other factors included degree of competition, strength of demand, the

state of the local economy, relative costs, and economies of scale. Though there was a minimal decrease of profitability, the funeral industry still had healthy profitability growth.

Section 3. Factors Affecting Good Financial Performance of the Funeral Industry towards Competitive Advantage

This section discusses the factors affecting financial performance of the funeral businesses towards competitive advantage, including the assessment of the external environment using the Porter’s Five Forces and the PESTLE, which stands for Political, Economic, Social, and Technological, Legal, and environmental factors.

3.1 External Factors using Porter's Five Forces for Analyzing the Business’ Competitive Advantage

A. Bargaining Power of the Consumers

Table 18. *Range of Package Price*

Funeral Industry	Standard Package Price	COVID-positive Package
A	25,000 to 600,000	N/A
B	20,000-250,000	N/A
C	20,000-500,000	25,000
D	35,000-500,000	25,000
E	26,000-150,000	N/A
F	18,000-150,000	N/A
G	15,000-150,000	N/A

The bargaining power of consumers included free-will to choose from the different standard package price offered by the funeral businesses. For funeral industry customers, one wanted to avail the funeral service only when the funeral would give discount. Otherwise, a customer may transfer or switch to other funeral with lower price package. All the respondents shared that “maghahanap sila ng mura na package na abot ng budget nila at laging nasusunod gusto ng customers, kumbaga, customers are always right, if may gusto sila idagdag sa package like for example, mga pamahiin sa kabaong (interior ng kabaong), napapag-usapan naman lahat. Kung may gusto sila ipadagadag at kaya naman ibigay ng libre, why not? Pero kung hindi naman kaya, napapag-usapan naman” (the customer’s choice will always prevail because customers are always right). Based on the result of interview with the owner and manager, the funeral businesses within the province tended to lower their prices, therefore, they were price sensitive in order to catch more customers. The bargaining power of consumers was very dynamic and also depended on the flexibility of the bargaining approach. Individual personal finances were affected by expenditures (Jack et.al. 2019).

All funeral businesses only catered to an average of two customers a week. Customers came within their respective municipalities. Others were recommended by

their contact key persons from the hospitals, the Philippine National Police (PNP), and from the Municipal Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (MDRRMO). The customers were free to choose a package they were able and comfortable of paying and bargained in case of financial difficulties. Funeral H did not offer bargain because it was a pre-need company. Pre-need memorial plans were permanent life insurance covering the expense of funeral care and burial, therefore, it had fixed costs and charges and had guaranteed price, even during inflation. It did not require to make up the difference. Also, there was no cost incurred when the customer changed buying preferences except for upgrading the package and incurring add-ons. If ever customers had difficulty in their finances, they would not shift to other competitors, but instead bargained or haggled and asked for extension of payments. There were also instances where the embalming services were to be availed of and the coffin was already purchased in other shop ahead of time. This was called “Redeemer Plan”. Consumer behavior had changed in favor of a better assessment of the different possibilities of services supplied and of their relative prices (Blayac, Bougette and Montet, 2014).

Based on the result of Profitability ratios, there was a good Profit Margin ratio. It was desirable since it meant the business generated more profits from its sales. The funeral industry business was one of the most profitable businesses because consumers wanted to pay dearly to get the best funeral service for their departed loved ones. Consumer spending for these needs was high indicating that funeral industry had good financial prospects.

B. Bargaining Power of Suppliers

The bargaining power of suppliers played significant role in the funeral industry market because there would always be unexpected deaths, supplies were needed, and services were launched every death. The prices of coffins from Pampanga and embalming medicines from Ramon, Isabela were pegged amidst the pandemic. The terms of payment even toned easier at a 60 days payment for coffins and higher discount price if paid in cash, about three to five percent range of discount. Medicines were all in cash basis. During the pandemic, COVID-positive cadavers did not need coffins. However, the need for Body bag and PPEs were purchased in cash basis within twenty four hours because the bodies must be buried right away, unless the bereaved family chose to have it cremated. According to the respondents, *“Wala naman nagbago sa terms and conditions ng pag –order ng kabaong at gamot before and during the Pandemic. Hindi rin mahirap kausapin mga suppliers namen kasi nakapag-build na kami ng very good working relationships sa kanila, magkakaiba man kami ng suppliers ng kabaong pero lahat from Pampanga, pero iisa lang naman sa gamot na pinagkukunan namen which is from IPI (International Pharmaceutical Incorporated) na may pinaka malapit na branch sa Ramon, Isabela”*. *“Sa kabaong, usually, 60 days ang term of payment, pero kapag naic-cash namen, may discount na at least 5%. Sa gamot ay cash basis kami. Wala actually problema sa suppliers ever since kasi halos hindi naman nag increase ang presyo ng kabaong at gamot, kung meron man sobrang minimal lang”* (Nothing has changed in the terms and conditions of ordering coffins and medicine before and during the pandemic. The bargaining power of suppliers included negotiation over inclusion of a

supplier's product, conditions under which negotiation by suppliers increased the suppliers' bargaining power even when the suppliers' products were not substitutes for each other. In particular, negotiation increased the suppliers' bargaining power if suppliers faced smaller losses from disagreement when they negotiated (Craig, 2014).

All funeral businesses had two to three coffin suppliers, either wood or metal from Pampanga, but only Funeral H who was a Pre-need company purchased from La Union. Since the supplier was identified by the Main Office and dealt with centralized services and suppliers, it had full-service nationwide, and had identified supplier of mortuary supply down to funeral equipment. All funeral industries purchased their coffins in either cash basis or consignment for metal coffins. Embalming medicines were all cash purchases from the International Pharmaceutical Incorporated (IPI) with Head Office located in Cebu City and the nearest branch located was in Ramon, Isabela. According to the funeral industries, there were no better products other than the products by their own respective suppliers because they already built a long-term business relationship, trust, and loyalty for a very long time. However, the presence of powerful suppliers reduced the profit potential in the funeral industry. Suppliers increased competition by threatening to raise prices or reduce the quality of goods and services. As a result, they reduced profitability in funeral industries where businesses could not recover cost increases in their own prices.

As per data gathered, there was a decrease of liabilities which meant that all funeral businesses had the capability to pay its short-term and long-term liabilities. It should be noted that becoming more financially flexible due to having low-to zero liabilities might be seen as positive sign.

Potential Development of Substitute Products

As to services, traditional funeral service followed a commonly known service structure, as well as a common committal (burial) ceremony. However, in modern day society, people were no longer limited to one funeral service option. Customers tended to personalize and individualize bereavement services, Contemporary Funeral service included a *Celebration of Life*. Funeral services were not limited to a particular location, from flowers present at the service, to pictures and memorabilia featured, and physical objects and personal favorites of the deceased may be used to tailor a more individualized approach in honoring a loved one. The potential rise in crematorium was an element of contemporary funerals which included themed funeral and its "Novelty", for example, Chinese funeral. Burial was traditionally favoured in Chinese funerals but with a rapidly expanding population, cremation was becoming more common. Chinese burial practice dictated that the location of Chinese graves (which were usually mound-shaped) be chosen according to the complicated laws of feng shui. In Indian funeral, the casket was carried into the crematorium feet first while mourners recited prayers, an open casket displayed the deceased, and guests were expected to view the body. In Muslim funeral, Muslims were always buried and never cremated. It was a religious requirement that the body be ritually washed and draped before burial which should be as soon as possible after death.

Moreover, as to medicine supplies used in embalming, substitutes were not yet considered because there was no potential development of formalin product substitute. Formalin is a universal fixative and was routinely used as a preservative for dead bodies. As to other supplies like coffin, based on the data gathered from the respondents, there was a higher cost of production than that of purchasing a ready-made coffin from their respective suppliers. Therefore, it made funeral industry more attractive. In addition, it increased profit. Conversely, a high threat of substitute products made an industry less attractive. Mortuary products were considered “gold standard” due to ease of availability and cost-effectiveness. In spite of these advantages, it emphasized that for now, there was no safer alternative supplies for embalming (Chittemsetti et al., 2018). However, the threat of substitution products or services in a funeral industry affected the competitive environment for the funeral industry and influenced those funeral businesses’ ability to achieve profitability like cremation. The availability of substitution services affected the profitability of a funeral industry because consumers could choose to purchase the substitute instead of the traditional funeral services (Financial Leadership, 2014).

Based on the data gathered, all funeral businesses were liquid. Whilst from an owner’s perspective this might seem favourable, having too high liquidity ratios might mean that the resources of the funerals were being sidelined when cash on hand could be used to expand operations such as crematorium or improve existing non-current assets such as equipment to improve profitability.

C. Potential entry of new competitors

Funeral industry required high capitalization, competition with prepaid funeral plans, high-pressure coffin and medicine prices, and over all effective management. Therefore, potential competitors had difficulty entering the traditional industry because it required much capital and background and passion in handling dead bodies. Based on the data gathered from the owners and managers and some key employees, it was difficult to build or start a funeral business due to fact that there were numerous business requirements, apart from choosing a strategic location approved by the DENR, and the LGU. It was also very difficult to sustain the operation because there were already many funeral businesses in the province. According to the respondents *“mahirap magpatayo ngayon ng punerarya sa dami ng business requirements at kailangan ng malaking capital, i-consider mo din location na malayo na sa bahay-bahay dapat, kasi strikto na din ang DENR as to location. Kami na nakapag-patayo na nauna, before pa mga laws na yan, nakapili kami ng strategic location kung saan nakatayo ngayon mga punerarya namin. If in case may gusto magpatayo ng business na ganito, medyo mahihirapan pa din sya na maging stable at i-sustain dahil marami na rin punerarya dito sa atin. Kaming nagtagal na sa negosyong ‘ito, masasabi naming Insitution na kami, mapagkakatiwalaan na sa serbisyo na binibigay namin”*. In addition, *“hindi ka rin pwede magpatayo ng punerarya ng wala kang licensed embalmer”*. (It is difficult to build or start a funeral business due to the fact that there were numerous business requirements and the need for a large capital, you should also consider a location that is far from residences and houses, because the DENR is also strict as to location. Long before our funeral started, we were able to choose the most strategic location where our business is situated right now. If in case someone

wants to build a business like this, it will still be a bit difficult for him to become stable and be able to sustain its operation because there are already many funeral homes here. We have been in this business for quite a long time, we can say that we are already an Institution, our community already trusted the service we provide. Moreover, you also cannot build a funeral business without a licensed embalmer). Potential entry of new competitors could both make a funeral industry more competitive and decrease profit potential for existing funerals.

All businesses in the funeral industry had the same embalming procedure therefore there was no competition with regard to embalming procedure except for Funeral H who had expertise in make-up and used the brand Max-Factor as make-up for longer time period because it was less greasy. Forty four percent were motivated to enter the industry because of the high profit involved and they needed to supplement their income (Waithaka, 2001).

The entry of a new competitor in the market tended to reduce the market prices. Potential entry of cremation would affect the market share because when there were more funeral businesses competing and one was new in the arena for the same market share, customers chose those with lower pricing, and the general price level would go down. Therefore, it could affect the financial performance of the funeral business. The variables that affected potential entry of new competitors like barriers, costs, prices, and competitors influenced the performance of the funeral business that caused changes to maintain their market position.

The entry of a new competitor in a market would affect greatly the Gross Profit margin rate which measured the reasonability of the price of the services of each funeral. Generally, the higher, the better. But too high might mean the services of products were overpriced in order to accommodate their operating expenses.

D. Rivalry among Competing Firms

There was an intense rivalry among funeral businesses in the province because there were eight competing firms. High intensity of competitive funeral industry rivalry could make a funeral more competitive and thus decrease profit potential. In comparison, low intensity of competitive funeral industry rivalry would make an industry less competitive. It also increased profit potential for the existing funerals. Funeral industry outside the province which offered crematory services were part of the competing players within the industry.

All funeral businesses offered free service for babies who died below one month old. Funeral H had unique promo for deceased teachers, either private or public school teacher, provided that they die within the "Teachers Day month" which is the month of October. Funeral F offered to all its employees free funeral service in case of death, and fifty percent for immediate family members. All funeral industry within Vizcaya were all competitors considering customers could avail any of the funeral services. However, Funeral G had an advantage of being the only funeral industry in the town and residents

availed its services automatically regardless if some funeral offered cheaper price. Some customers tended to shift to other competitors for cheaper price and discount on credit. Consumers would not shift to other competitors simply for the reason that these consumers were loyal to their particular funeral because they already had prior experience of the services besides word-of-mouth advertisements. The competition as non-aggressive maintained the prices in the provincial range as the main business strategy. The high demand and low competition resulted in simple and less innovative strategies and especially with low-cost advertising (Anacleto et al., 2019). The opportunity to have crematory services in the province might increase profit because they did not need to transport the cadaver and avail their services.

An Asset Turnover ratio of value 0.25 to 0.5 was considered as a 'good' total turnover asset for the industry as the total assets were able to produce enough revenue at the end of the year. However, due to the negative impact of the pandemic, Funerals E and F had declined in their sales which also caused the decline of their asset turnover ratio because of the effect of the pandemic in which they were not accredited by the LGU to service or cater to COVID-positive cadavers.

Moreover, based on the data provided by the owners and managers, there was no closure plans for the funeral business since they were profitable.

Based on the data gathered, though there was a minimal decrease of profitability, the funeral industry still had healthy profitability growth. Due to market liberalization, a business had the ability to increase its profit, to survive, and be competitive (Yazdanfar, 2013).

3.2 External Factors using PESTLE which stands for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, and Environmental factors

Political Factors

The political factors determined the extent to which a government may influence the funeral industry. The required business taxes were promptly paid. Paying the right amount of tax and on-time provided good business reputation. Also, the higher the income and tax they declared, the higher the credit rating. The governments could raise or lower business tax, which would impact on funeral industry profits. They could bring in new laws like the National Minimum Wage, which would impact on profits and employment rights. It is important to keep a reasonable ratio of current assets to current liabilities to ensure that short-term obligations could be paid on time, opportunities for volume expansion could be seized, and unforeseen circumstances could be handled easily. The appropriate magnitude for this ratio varied widely among industries, companies, and the specific circumstances of individual companies. However, a popular rule of thumb was that a company's current ratio should be at least 2 is to 1.

Trade restrictions for funeral industry was stated in the DOH memorandum No. 2020-0158 subject on Proper Handling of the Remains of Suspect, Probable, and Confirmed COVID-19 Cases. Moreover, the tariff policies that affected funeral industry

included exemption from VAT when provided by an undertaker or embalmer as part of a funeral package that included the disposal of the remains of the dead, supply of a coffin, the cover and fittings for a coffin, the casket, and urn or scatter tube.

At the local government setting, some politicians endorsed a particular funeral service and sponsored the funeral service of the deceased. Funeral A's owner was a municipal councilor, and Funeral G's owner's wife was also a municipal councilor, but as far as politics was concerned, there was no political problems where the business was situated. Local government must extend support and protect it against politicking and eventual loss of culture and family (Derogongan, Agosto, and Bariñan, 2019).

Based on the data gathered, it is important to keep a reasonable ratio of current assets to current liabilities to ensure that short-term obligations could be paid on time, opportunities for volume expansion could be seized, and unforeseen circumstances could be handled easily. The funeral businesses had a current ratio of more than one. It is a good indicator that it could cover its current liabilities on time. Outside creditors would consider this a positive data to finance the business whenever a need of loan arises.

Economic Factors

Economic Factors took into account the various aspects of the economy and how the outlook on each area could impact the funeral industry.

The combination of high poverty and low political stability made the province more responsive to the increasing financial burden of death costs on households prompting them to a more active interference into funeral regulation (Sadigov, 2020). Regardless of the social class level of a customer, funeral industries had guaranteed income for whatever packages they might avail. The economic and market conditions seemed almost did not affect the purchase of coffins and embalming medicines from the suppliers amidst the pandemic. The terms of payment were even toned easier at 60 days for coffins and on a consignment basis in Pampanga because during the pandemic, COVID-positive cadavers did not need coffins and within 24 hours, the bodies must be buried, unless the bereaved family chose to have it cremated.

Even in death, the spirit of inflation crept into the grave. There was no escaping the constant increase in prices. One of which was the soaring prices of the commodities that limited the purchasing power of the consumers, the fuel prices, and lastly, the call for salary increase. The funeral industry, like any other companies, also needed to survive although the price increase on the funeral services was not so significant and reasonable. The volatile prices of fuel from the foreign market greatly affected the business. Ninety percent of the fuel requirement in the Philippines were imported internationally. Cremation, for example, was affected by the fuel increase plus the logistics fleet. Indirectly, the increase in the electricity rate had also affected the business. Aside from the oil price increase, another factor that caused inflation was the insufficient rice supply and the exchange rate against the US dollar. The Philippine peso had been weak since the US increased its interest rates, according to the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI). The Tax Reform for Acceleration and Inclusion known as TRAIN Law, however,

had a very low contribution. Under this law, the employees had higher take-home wages. The problem was the prices of the commodities such as rice, toiletries, and utilities had gone high forcing the workers to call for a salary hike. Funeral H which was into pre-need had an advantage. It would allow clients to pay a small amount every month for 5 years. Instalments were affordable and memorial plans were transferable, assignable, and were not affected by inflation. Funeral H had complete memorial services to all plans, plus value added benefits like Cash Benefit, Waiver of Instalments, Unpaid Balance Deemed Paid, and Accidental Death and Dismemberment. This way it would not be so much of a burden to cash out a huge amount when the time comes.

Moreover, unemployment rates affected funeral business in way that when bereaved family had more unemployed members, they tended to choose the cheapest package available leading to minimal income to the funeral business.

The factors mentioned above directly influenced the financial performance of the funeral industry. However, since funeral service was a must, they had guaranteed income and financial stability with competitive earnings. As an indicator of efficiency, there must be profit. A financial gain was the earnings from sales or revenue after deduction of all costs, including interest payment on debt and tax (Bashar and Islam, 2014). The Return on Assets (ROA) result indicated that the funeral industry was able to maximize the use of its assets for getting more profits. The Return on Equity (ROE) result indicated that the funeral industry was more effective at generating profit from its existing assets. Likewise, the business that increased in its ROE over time was likely getting more efficient.

Social Factors

Social factors were related to the cultural and demographic trends of society. Social norms and pressures were key to determining consumer behavior. Consumer behavior helped funeral industry determine what services to offer. When they knew what customers buy and how they went about buying those services, the funeral could more easily spot a need that had not yet been satisfied. Moreover, when funeral industry knew how customers behaved in relation to the services they were selling, they had better understanding of how to provide good service to them, increasing the chance for repeat customers and contributing to their profitability.

Arranging a funeral was a complex socio-emotional process that crystallized multiple affects (McManus and Schafer, 2014). Often, cultural norms and practices were tied with religious beliefs, including the beliefs around what happens after a person dies. There was a correlation between religiosity and purchase intention (Katan et al., 2019). The Ifugaos believed in the immortality of the soul so much so that the dead was given elaborate ceremonies consisting of daily butchering of animals until the body was buried. Embalming was not a part of their practice. However, it seemed to be vanishing. The cadavers decayed faster without embalming. Liquid and blood from the cadaver would visibly run out from the body and other undesired effects of decomposition. In today's health protocols, Ifugaos already embraced the funeral services provided some practices like sharp nails in the coffin must be changed and had it double foamed because the body might be hurt and the bereaved family might be haunted by the soul of the deceased

family member. In today's situation, customers were still more on traditional funeral rather than cremation, except for COVID-positive cadavers in which protocols were strictly adhered to. Traditional funeral service was cheaper compared to cremation. For pre-need memorial service, avilment of such may require age limit up to sixty five years old without pre-existing conditions upon avilment and one year contingency period. Population growth is an advantage, because mortality rate goes hand-in-hand. Health consciousness had significant negative effect on the mortality rate. Health consciousness could lower death rate through health life goals and perceived behavioural control.

Career attitudes of customers affected the funeral industry's profitability by providing information and suggestions how to improve their services. Foundations of families that were more homogeneous in terms of educational backgrounds and financial resources also tended to support upward social mobility (Noll, 2016).

Social factors as mentioned above influenced actions when it came to managing finances. Also, these were proof that all social factors incremented financial resources, and vice versa. Increased financial performances led to greater social benefits. Based on the data gathered, the Profitability ratios used like Net Profit Margin ratio, Gross Profit ratio, Return on Asset, and Return on Equity reflected the combined effects of liquidity and management in handling the assets and liabilities on the operating results of the funeral business.

Technological Factors

The technology investment of funeral industry would reduce production costs contributing to increased profits. It reduced transaction costs because customers could buy cheaper package with unchanged quality. Technological advances had made it possible for Funeral Industry to be more efficient, capture more opportunities, boost customer loyalty and, most importantly, make more money. Without a doubt, technology had enhanced efficiency and convenience in handling Funeral Industry that made the Funeral Industry business world competitive. Technology produced efficiency and reduced marketing costs, challenges were easier to identify, organization and time tracking became better, business safety improved, and overall costs were reduced.

Technological factors were linked to innovation in the funeral industry as well as innovation in the overall economy. The "modern" or traditional funeral, as it was known in the Funeral Industry today, included embalming, coffin, service, and burial in a cemetery which was still practiced until now. No automation of the traditional service could replace it. Therefore, technological advances in the funeral service had yet to be considered according to the respondents. Funeral H, the largest Filipino Pre-need Deathcare company together with Filipino Tech Startup: Kezar Atlas Technologies launched the Mobile Application for the public on November 15, 2019, which was available for both Android and iOS, aimed to modernize the funeral industry with innovative features such as "Funeral H Gate" which created profile for the deceased loved one to receive messages and prayers online and "E-Burol Funeral Viewing" that allowed families and friends to view Funeral H wakes from anywhere in the world (www.stpeter.com). By

improving business processes, technology increased productivity in various funeral operations like the use of email and social media which had made communication easier and faster.

Moreover, advances in research and development affected technology, and eventually improved an economy's rate of productivity. Based on the data gathered from the owners and manager, technological development in the funeral industry involved consumer access to the Internet, social networks, and technology associated with logistics. Technological advances had made it possible for funeral industry to be more efficient, capture more opportunities, boost customer loyalty and, most importantly, make more money. Technology produced efficiency, reduced marketing costs, easier to identify challenges, better organization and time tracking, improved business safety, and reduced overall costs. Based on the data gathered, the more advanced the technology was, the more profitable the business would be. In line with this, the efficiency ratios of the funeral businesses measured how well the funeral industry was managing its assets. The asset turnover ratio was generally used to determine the efficiency of the business in using its resources like social media to generate sales.

Legal Factors

Legal factors pertained to any legal forces that defined what a business could or could not do. Funeral homes received most of the benefits of regulation (Ellig, 2015). According to the respondents, industry regulations governing funeral industry included Presidential Decree No. 856 December 23, 1975, Code On Sanitation, Chapter Xxi Disposal Of Dead Persons, Sec.93-98. The licences and permits needed for the operation were Bureau of Internal Revenue TIN, Barangay Clearance, Department of Trade and Industry Business Name Registration Certificate, Mayor's Permit/ Business Permit, SEC Registration Certificate (for Partnership and Corporation), Fire Safety Inspection Certificate (FSIC), Sanitary Permit, and DENR Permit. Among the government-mandated permits were SSS Employer's Registration which would ensure that employees were covered with insurance benefits like sickness, disability, maternity and death in accordance with Republic Act No. 8282. PhilHealth Employer's Registration would cover their employees' health insurance. Pag-ibig Employer's Registration would benefit employees who intended to apply for housing loan. Also, Labor Laws governing the funeral industry was DOLE Book IV which stated Health, Safety, and Social Welfare Benefits.

Being legally in operation ensured the legitimacy of the funeral industry as a legal entity to make profit and tax-status operation. Further, it ensured compliance with legal standards for bookkeeping and accounting. This established that the funeral industry was paying taxes and employees were covered under adequate insurance and the business was reporting income to the government. Also, it established consumers' trust when a funeral industry was legally operating. Legally operating funeral industries also made them eligible to receive supplier discounts that they would not normally receive as an unregistered operation.

Such legal factors played a big part in deciding how funeral industry businesses operated and what profits they received as well as how customers and employees behaved. Also, these legal factors played an important role in determining the success rate of funeral industry businesses and how it affected the financial performance of the funeral industry. The Government could levy taxes on funeral industry among the regulatory activities which protected costumers, employees, and the entrepreneurs. Based on the data gathered, there was a good profit margin ratio. It was desirable since it meant the funeral industry generated more profits from its sales. The Gross profit margin rates were healthy which meant that the funeral industry did well in managing its cost of sales. It also showed that the business had more to cover for operating, financing, and other costs.

Environmental Factors

Environmental factors were also sometimes called 'ecological factors' which affected the operation of the funeral industry. Environmental factors referred to variables regarding the physical environment. This could include things like climate change, temperature, the availability of energy, or any direct consequences of these things. It had significant positive and negative impact on profitability because these environmental factors could produce both psychological distress and additional costs burdens for Funeral Industry owners.

Environmental factors focused on the ecological impacts on funeral industry and how to adapt to these changes. Environmental factors like weather conditions, temperature climate change, and pollution did not affect the Funeral Industry. The respondents said "*Bumabagyo man o umaaraw, tuloy pa din ang pagserbisyo sa patay, kasi wala naman pinipiling oras at panahon ang kamatayan*". (Even if the weather is stormy or sunny, services for the dead continues because death does not choose the hour or the time). However, in terms of natural phenomenon like pandemic, for Funeral E and F, they mentioned it was a disadvantage and affected profitability. Funeral E did not accept COVID-positive cadavers because bereaved families tended not to pay the services or on-credit, while Funeral F was not an accredited funeral industry to cater to COVID-positive cadavers in the municipality.

Environmental factors had positive and negative significant impact on profitability because these factors could produce both psychological distress and additional costs burden funeral industry owners. The data gathered showed that there was minimal decrease of profitability. The funeral industry still had healthy profitability growth amidst environmental factors.

To summarize the factors affecting financial performance of the funeral businesses towards competitive advantage, these included the assessment of the external environment using Porter's Five Forces and the PESTLE. Under Porter's Five Forces, *Bargaining power of the consumers* included free-will to choose from the different standard package price offered by the funeral businesses. Based on the result of Profitability ratios, there was a good Profit Margin ratio. It was desirable since it meant

the business generated more profits from its sales. The funeral industry business was one of the most profitable businesses because consumers wanted to pay dearly to get the best funeral service for their departed loved ones. Consumer spending for these needs was high indicating that funeral industry had good financial prospects.

Bargaining power of suppliers played a significant role in the funeral industry market because there would always be unexpected deaths, supplies were needed, and services were launched every death. As per data gathered, there is a decrease of liabilities which means that all funeral businesses have the capability to pay its short-term and long-term liabilities. It should be noted that becoming more financially flexible due to having low-to zero liabilities might be seen as positive sign.

Potential development of substitute products in a funeral industry affected the competitive environment for the funeral industry and influenced those funeral businesses' ability to achieve profitability like cremation. Based on the data gathered, all funeral businesses were liquid whilst from an owner's perspective this might seem favourable. Having too high liquidity ratios might mean that the resources of the funerals were being sidelined when cash on hand could be used to expand operations such as crematorium or improve existing non-current assets such as equipment to improve profitability.

Potential entry of new competitors in the funeral industry required high capitalization, competition with prepaid funeral plans, high-pressure coffin and medicine prices, and over all effective management. The entry of a new competitor in a market affected greatly the Gross Profit margin rate which measured the reasonability of the price of the services of each funeral. Generally, the higher the better. But too high might mean the services of products were overpriced in order to accommodate their operating expenses.

Rivalry among competing firms. There was an intense rivalry among funeral businesses in the province because there were eight competing firms. High intensity competition among the funeral industry could make a funeral business more competitive and thus decrease profit potential. However, due to the negative impact of the pandemic, Funerals E and F had declined in their sales which also caused the decline of their asset turnover ratio. Because of the pandemic, they were not accredited by the LGU to service or cater to COVID-positive cadavers. Also, based on the data gathered, though there was a minimal decrease of profitability, the funeral industry still had healthy profitability growth. Due to market liberalization, a business had ability to increase its profit, to survive, and be competitive (Yazdanfar, 2013).

External Factors using PESTLE included political factors which determined the extent to which a government may influence the funeral industry. The required business taxes were promptly paid. Paying the right amount of tax and on-time provided good business reputation. Also, the higher the income and tax they declare, the higher the credit rating. The government could raise or lower business tax, which would impact on funeral industry profits. Based on the data gathered, it was important to keep a reasonable ratio of current assets to current liabilities to ensure that short-term obligations could be paid on time, opportunities for volume expansion could be seized, and unforeseen

circumstances could be handled easily. The funeral businesses had a current ratio of more than one. It was a good indicator that it could cover its current liabilities on time. Outside creditors would consider this a positive data to finance the business whenever a need of loan arises. *Economic factors* took into account the various aspects of the economy, and how the outlook on each area could impact the funeral industry. It directly influenced the financial performance funeral industry. However, since funeral service was a must, they had guaranteed income and financial stability with competitive earnings. As an indicator of efficiency, there must be profit. It was a financial gain. It was the earnings from sales or revenue after deduction of all costs, including interest payment on debt and tax (Bashar and Islam, 2014). The Return on Assets (ROA) result indicated that the funeral industry was able to maximize the use of its assets for getting more profits. The Return on Equity (ROE) result indicated that the funeral industry was more effective at generating profit from its existing assets. Likewise, the business that increased in its ROE over time was likely getting more efficient.

Social factors increment financial resources, and vice versa. Increased financial performances lead to greater social benefits. Based on the data gathered, the Profitability ratios used like Net Profit Margin ratio, Gross Profit ratio, Return on Asset, and Return on Equity reflected the combined effects of liquidity and management in handling the assets and liabilities on the operating results of the funeral business.

Technological factors such as technological advances had made it possible for funeral industry to be more efficient, capture more opportunities, boost customer loyalty and, most importantly, make more money. Technology produced efficiency, reduced marketing costs, easier to identify challenges, better organization and time tracking, improved business safety, and reduced overall costs. Based on the data gathered, the more advanced the technology is, the more profitable the business will be. In line with this, the efficiency ratios of the funeral businesses measured how well the funeral industry was managing its assets. The asset turnover ratio was generally used to determine the efficiency of the business in using its resources like social media to generate sales.

Legal factors played a big part in deciding how funeral industry businesses operated and what profits they received, as well as how customers and employees behaved. Also, these legal factors played an important role in determining the success rate of funeral industry businesses and how these affected the financial performance of the funeral industry. The Government could levy taxes on funeral industry among the regulatory activities which protected the costumers, employees, and the entrepreneurs. Based on the data gathered, there was a good profit margin ratio. It was desirable since it meant the funeral industry generated more profits from its sales. The Gross profit margin rates were healthy which meant that the funeral industry did well in managing its cost of sales. It also showed that the business had more to cover for operating, financing, and other costs.

Environmental factors had positive and negative significant impact on profitability because these factors could produce both psychological distress and additional costs burden for funeral industry owners. Results showed that there was a minimal decrease

of profitability. The funeral industry still had healthy profitability growth amidst environmental factors.

Section 4. The Challenges in the Funeral Industry Operations Encountered Before and During the Pandemic Under External Factors

Bargaining Power of Buyers

Bargaining power of Buyers included their free-will to choose from the funeral industry of their choice. However, buyers made *“tawad-sagad”* (bargain for the lowest fixed-price) if they were financially distressed. Porter's Five Forces framework referred to the pressure that buyers could put on funeral businesses to get them to provide higher quality products, better customer service, and/or lower prices. All the respondents shared that *“Laging nasusunod gusto ng customers, kumbaga, customers are always right, if may gusto sila idagdag sa package like for example, mga pamahiin sa kabaong (interior ng kabaong), napapag-usapan naman lahat. Kung may gusto sila ipadagdag at kaya naman ibigay ng libre, why not? Pero kung hindi naman kaya, napapag-usapan naman”* (The customers' choice will always prevail because customers are always right. For example, if a customer wants to customize the coffin's interior due to tradition, and requires minimal expense on our part, it is given for free of charge; however, if it is not, everything can be bargained). Another respondent said that one of the challenges was that *“Kung may unclaimed salvage victims , it will be automatically a loss sa amin kasi, regardless kung may mag claim or wala, the funeral will still performs its standard services in coordination with the Philippine National Police (PNP)”* (Unclaimed salvage victims' cadaver is automatically a loss, and regardless if claimed or unclaimed, the funeral will still perform its standard procedure and services in coordination with the Philippine National Police). Another one was, during the pandemic, Funeral A shared *“Tinakbuhan kami ng namatayan, dala pati patay, hindi na nagbayad sa kasunduan date, at wala na kami magagawa nun”* (The bereaved family ran away from us, carrying the dead and did not pay on the agreed date, and there was nothing we could do then). However, prior to accepting a cadaver, contract had been signed by both parties. As stated in the contract, settlement of payment must be done on or before the burial. But in some instances wherein the bereaved family had financial difficulties, extension of payment for one week was acceptable. *“ Ang hirap naman pilitin kung wala naman pambayad, or hirap sa napagkasunduan terms and conditions, so, wala kami magawa kundi maghintay, kasi kung kakasuhan naman namen, mas mahal pa ‘yung pag-file ng kaso keysa sa masisingil namen”* (It is difficult to force payment if there is no money to pay, or to settle payment based on the agreed terms and conditions, so, we can do nothing but wait, because if we will file a case, it is more expensive than the amount to be collected).

Funerals A and D shared that during the pandemic, *“Sa ayaw at sa gustuhin man ng namatayan ng COVID-positive, need nila bayaran body bag na gagamitin sa patay, PPE ng mga maglilibing at iba pang kailangan na nakasaad sa protocol”* (Bereaved family members of COVID-positive cadavers, whether they like it or not, need to pay for the body bag used on the deceased, PPE of the undertakers, and other necessities stated in the protocol).

The consumers made an informed choice by ensuring that relevant prices for similar goods and services were disclosed (van der Laan, & Moerman, 2017). Perception and understanding of customers in the funeral service development significantly influenced the preferences of funeral services or the intention to purchase innovation to the development in funeral services (Sam Sam, 2014).

An Asset Turnover ratio of value 0.25 to 0.5 was considered as a 'good' total turnover asset for the industry as the total assets were able to produce enough revenue at the end of the year. However, due to the negative impact of the pandemic, Funerals E and F had declined in their sales which also caused the decline of their asset turnover ratio.

Bargaining Power of Suppliers

According to the respondents, the COVID-19 pandemic had a differing impact on different value chains of the funeral industry, as well as within each individual value chain. While the impact of demand reductions would eventually affect all producers in the value chain, the financial burden was unlikely to be shared equally by producers across the chain. Measures were taken by producers to protect their own cash position. However, in case of funeral industry in Nueva Vizcaya, there was still on-time and continuity of payments. The bargaining power of different suppliers in the chain was key in determining which chain partners would manage to avoid costs. For this reason, suppliers patronized their own funeral industries because they already built good business relationship long before the pandemic and during the pandemic. According to the respondents, *“Wala naman nagbago sa terms and conditions ng pag-order ng kabaong at gamot before and during the Pandemic. Hindi rin mahirap kausapin mga suppliers namen kasi nakapag-build na kami ng very good working relationships sa kanila, magkakaiba man kami ng suppliers ng kabaong pero lahat from Pampanga, pero iisa lang naman sa gamot na pinagkukunan namen which is from IPI (International Pharmaceutical Incorporated) na may pinaka malapit na branch sa Ramon, Isabela”*. *“Sa kabaong, usually, 60 days ang term of payment, pero kapag naicash namen, may discount na at least 5%. Sa gamot ay cash basis kami. Wala actually problema sa suppliers ever since kasi halos hindi naman nag increase ang presyo ng kabaong at gamot, kung meron man sobrang minimal lang”* (Nothing has changed in the terms and conditions of ordering coffins and medicine before and during the pandemic. It was also not difficult to talk to suppliers because we had already built a very good working relationships with them, although we have different suppliers of coffins but all are from Pampanga, but we only have one supplier of embalming medicines, which is from IPI (International Pharmaceutical Incorporated) with the nearest branch in Ramon, Isabela. As to coffins, usually, the payment term is 60 days, but when it is paid on cash, 5% discount is given. As to medicines, we are on cash basis. There is actually no problem with suppliers ever since because the price of coffins and medicines have hardly increased).

Innovative creativity was manifested in the provision of funeral services between suppliers and Funeral Industry with observations on the contemporary shift and its background framework of a 'good funeral' (Tanaka, 2012).

Potential development of substitutes

According to the funeral industries, they had no ability to produce or develop substitute products except for two funeral industries, Funeral F and G who tried to produce their own coffins but due to lack of expertise in carving and carpentry, and due to lack of expert carpenters, it was disregarded as potential development in their business. All the respondents shared that *“Mas advantageous ang bumili ng ready-made na kabaong keysa mag-maintain ng 2-3 na karpintero na expert sa paggawa ng kabaong, mas malaki ‘yung cost. Sa gamot naman, walang pwedeng alternative sa pang embalsamo. Yun lang talaga ‘yung gamot na gagamitin, unless may sariling chemist at laboratory ang punerarya, pero hindi rin ‘eto possible.”* (It is more advantageous to buy ready-made coffin than to maintain 2-3 carpenters who are experts in making coffins, the cost is greater. In medicine, there is no alternative medicine to embalming. We use only one prescribed embalming medicines, unless the funeral home has its own chemist and laboratory, but this is also not possible).

Potential entry of new competitors

The vital motivation of entry into the funeral arena was anticipated high profits (Wanjiru, 2001). Anticipated high profits played a role key in motivating entry (Waithaka, 2001). All manager or owners were licensed embalmers. They were given the Certificate from the Examiners for Undertakers and Embalmers (CEUE) from the Department of Health. The CEUE conducted licensure examination for embalmers twice a year (March and September). The examination consisted of two (2) parts: written and oral or practical. The examinee had to pass the written examination to qualify for the oral or practical examination. Once the examinee passed the oral/practical examination, he or she would be issued the Certificate of Registration (COR) and the ID as a licensed embalmer and he or she could practice the profession in the country.

According to the respondents *“Mahirap magpatayo ngayon ng punerarya sa dami ng business requirements at kailangan ng malaking capital, i-consider mo din location na malayo na sa bahay-bahay dapat, kasi strikto na din ang DENR as to location. Kami na nakapag-patayo na nauna, before pa mga laws na yan, nakapili kami ng strategic location kung saan nakatayo ngayon mga punerarya namen. If in case may gusto magpatayo ng business na ganito, medyo mahihirapan pa din sya na maging stable at i-sustain dahil marami na rin punerarya dito sa atin. Kaming nagtagal na sa negosyong ‘ito, masasabi naming Institution na kami, mapagkakatiwalaan na sa serbisyo na binibigay namin”*. In addition, *“hindi ka rin pwede magpatayo ng punerarya ng wala kang licensed embalmer”*. (It is difficult to build or start a funeral industry due to the fact that there were numerous business requirements and the need for a large capital. You should also consider a location that is far from residences and houses because the DENR is also strict as to location. Long before our funeral started, we were able to choose the most strategic location where our business is situated right now. If in case someone wants to build a business like this, it will still be a bit difficult for him to become stable and be able to sustain its operation because there are already many funeral homes here. We have been in this business for quite a long time, we can say that we are already an Institution, our

community already trusted the service we provide. Moreover, you also cannot build a funeral industry without a licensed embalmer).

Rivalry among competing firms

Some individuals engaged into funeral industry continued operating funeral industries inherited from their parents and relatives but also turned to local politics (Lyons, 2016). Therefore, there was clearly money to be made in the Funeral Industry and because death was inevitable, there would always be a market everyday (Thompson, 2017).

The competitors were the main challenge of the funeral industry (Granada, 2019). According to the respondents, the challenge was to be the lowest-cost provider in order to gain customers. In Nueva Vizcaya, there was an intense rivalry among funerals that could limit profits and lead to competitive moves, including price cutting, increased advertising expenditures, or spending on service improvements and innovation. *“Nagkakatalo-talo na lang sa dame ng kakilala, connections, at gaano ka kabait at accomodating sa mga customers, kanya-kanyang loyal customers na lang yan”*. (It is matter of how many acquaintances you have and connections, and how kind and accommodating you are to customers. We have our own loyal customers). Funeral G had an advantage of being the only funeral industry in the town and residents availed its services automatically regardless if some funeral offered cheaper price. Some customers tended to shift to other competitors for cheaper price and discount on credit. Consumers were loyal to their particular funeral because they already had prior experience of the services besides word-of-mouth advertisements. According to the respondents *“ ‘Yung mga ibang customers, nag-i-scout pa din kung saan may pinaka murang punerarya, pero nevertheless, kung saan meron na silang prior experience na punerarya, dun na rin sila ulit mag-aavail ng services”*. (Other customers still tend to scout for the cheapest funeral service; nevertheless, if they already have prior experience with a particular funeral, they will still avail the services).

There was no statement given that sooner or later, the funeral would close because of external and internal factors. These funeral homes were already considered institutions in their respective towns considering the number of years in the business amidst pandemic. They also had trust funds, but Funeral H shared that it had billions in their Trust Fund in case of bankruptcy. It only entrusted its trust funds to the country's leading banks such as Bank of the Philippine Islands (BPI), Banco de Oro (BDO), Metrobank (MBTC), Landbank of the Philippines-UCPB (LBP), Rizal Commercial Banking Corporation (RCBC), UnionBank of the Philippines (UBP) and Security Bank and Trust Company (SBTC) for the protection and security of its planholders. All the Funeral Industry would not incur cost in case of closure.

At a glance, the challenges encountered by the funeral industry using Porter's Five Forces framework were the following: strong bargaining power of buyers by making bargains or haggles to lower the package price; the bargaining power of different suppliers in the chain was key in determining which chain partners would manage to avoid

costs; hiring a coffin expert carpenter was more costly than that of purchasing a ready-made coffin from their respective suppliers; there was difficulty in starting a funeral business due to fact that there were a lot of business requirements; need for a strategic location approved by the DENR and the LGU; passion in handling dead bodies; one must have a licensed embalmer; and there was an intense rivalry among funeral businesses in the province.

Moreover, challenges encountered by the funeral industry using PESTLE framework were adherence with the Government laws and regulations, inflation, flexibility in the deeply ingrained culture, varied traditions, beliefs and values, additional secondary services to combat trend, natural calamities and phenomena, and mandated business permits and licenses.

Section 5. The “Futures Thinking Model” for the Funeral Industry

The Futures Thinking Model for the Funeral Industry was crafted by adopting the required key elements from the Generic Foresight Process (GFP) Framework. It determined the current situations of the Funeral Industry along with the Traditional Service and changed drivers both internal and external factors. Given these premises, the researcher conducted interview, document scanning, and analysis of the same (documents) in order to interpret and determine what might happen in the future and be able to set a clear direction in the future.

Figure 4. *The “Futures Thinking Model” for the Funeral Industry*

The importance of proposing a Futures thinking mode was to help funeral industry managers or owners as well as employees understand the current situations, trends, and emerging issues and align their visions and serve as a road maps for a desired future. The informed preparedness was precisely why the futures thinking model was likewise important. It anticipated changes because it considered the complexity of the vast internal and external factors that can influence the outcome of a decision and to stay competitive.

With regard to the current industry situation, there was an intense competition and rivalry among competing players in the industry. Eight established and well-known funeral businesses in the province must stay profitable in order to stay competitive. The funeral businesses amidst the pandemic did not greatly affect their business operation. In fact, there were funeral businesses whose operations became favourable during the pandemic especially those which were accredited by the LGU to cater to COVID-positive cadavers. As to profitability, all the funeral businesses were efficiently handling all available resources based on the operating results of the business. The Profitability Ratios showed effectiveness of the funeral business operations. One of the current operations included traditional embalming process.

The key aspect of this model was foresight, which started with analysis. As shown in the model, there were changes in mortuary practices due to the disruption caused by the global pandemic such as the usual and predictable treatment for the deceased. Along the area of Interpretation, all funeral businesses were profitable and competitive because death is investable and provides recession-proof services thru test of time. Lastly, in terms of prospection, contemporary funeral services were often referred to as a celebration of life rather than death. This was due to these type of services being more personalized to the deceased individual and not following the traditional structure. In the contemporary funeral services, the location could be a park, pub, beach, or someone's home. Choosing a unique location allows for an individualized funeral celebration, and rituals could involve uncommon, or tailor-fitted, rituals to honor the deceased. These rituals did not usually follow traditional common practices and physical objects may be used to suit a more individualized approach to honoring a loved one.

The Futures Thinking Model for the funeral industry was expected to result to a re-engineered and diversified services of funeral businesses in a direction where they wanted to go to and understood and valued by consumers therefore increasing their profitability. The strategies included soft embalming, although the embalming process might not change. However, in today's modern day society, people were no longer limited to one and traditional funeral service option. Somehow, the Philippines could adopt soft-embalming, that required freezer because soft-embalming had limited time for open-coffin viewing. Furthermore, soft-embalmed cadavers have exceptional benefits, particularly for anatomical investigations and teaching, and since St. Mary's University offered BS Forensic Science, it could be of big help. Cost Sensitivity would hit rock bottom, there would be a large opportunity for firms who believed in supporting the emotional needs of those touched by death. Pre-Need plans would go through a major shift. The current business model struggled and as a result appeared to be working at odds with the funeral industry. This friction would come to a head. Smart business minds within the funeral profession would focus on it and new powerful solutions would emerge. Cremation would

hit up considering the industry started addressing some of the underlying issues brought on by the shift in pricing strategies and natural phenomena. There would be a unique spin on the traditional funeral designs to themed funerals because these were social events designed to give those attending the funeral a chance to pass on their respects to family members, and commemorate the life of the departed. Themed funerals were more personalized occasions, usually chosen by the deceased to reflect themselves. They could be themed around a personal passion, a special achievement, a favourite color or a much-loved place. Along with these strategies, competitive pricing created dynamism in the funeral market, like competing with cremation was partially a matter of price, but it was also a matter of convenience and even changing priorities. Therefore, building strong networking and business relationships created opportunities like meeting with all the members of the Philippine Mortuary association, sharing best practices and having conversations on their newest technology and innovation, and having dialogues with other industry connections. Intensive marketing efforts like social networks and viral marketing, paid media advertising, internet marketing, and conversational marketing must be opted for because these guaranteed profitability.

Conclusions

Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Most of the funeral industries in Nueva Vizcaya have single proprietorship as type of ownership and family owned. The oldest funeral industry has been in operation for 77 years. All the funeral industry have standard embalming to burial primary services. Their secondary services include Chapel with Wi-Fi, flowers, and lapida (tombstone). Their marketing platforms include Facebook Page, Word-of-mouth, Signage and Personal Selling. They work harmoniously with their linkages like their business suppliers.

In terms of financial performance, as to liquidity, all the funeral businesses have the ability to pay all short-term obligations on-time. Because they are liquid, the funeral businesses are capable of managing their finances without depending upon creditors for loans. They have very low debt-to-assets ratios which indicates the industries exceed their total amount of debts; therefore, the industries enjoy more financial flexibility which can be a factor to expand more aggressively since they do not need to spend a lot of money paying down debts. As to Efficiency Ratio (Asset Turnover ratio), the funeral businesses have good total assets that are able to produce enough revenues at the end of the year. As to Profitability, all the funeral businesses are efficiently handling all available resources on the operating results of the business. The Profitability Ratios used

show the effectiveness of the funeral business operations. Because they are liquid, cash are utilized at a favorable level. The level of profitability is also good.

The factors of good financial performance of the funeral industry towards competitive advantage conclude that, under the Porter's Five Forces, the bargaining power of consumers is very dynamic and also depends on the flexibility of bargaining approach; therefore, funeral businesses within the Province tend to lower their prices to catch more customers. All the Funeral businesses have strong working relationship with their own respective suppliers of coffins, flowers, printing service providers, and tombstone because they already built a long term business relationship, trust, and loyalty. As to mortuary supplies, substitutes are not yet considered as potential development for substitute products. Potential competitors have difficulty entering the industry because it required much capital and background and passion in handling dead bodies. Moreover, in the compliance of the different laws related to funeral business, all Funeral businesses within Nueva Vizcaya are all competitors considering customers can avail services from any of the funeral services. The funeral businesses also offer funeral benefits to all their employees and also funeral promos for walk-in customers. The funeral businesses amidst pandemic and other external or internal factors may not be greatly affected in their business operations and will not be a factor for future business closure. In terms of PESTLE, under political factors, there were no political affair involved in the operations where the business is situated. Moreover, the Local Government Units extend support by shouldering other expenses of the bereaved family and protect from politicking. Under Economic factors, poverty is not a hindrance in availing funeral services because it is a need. Inflation limits the purchasing power of the consumers; nevertheless, they will still avail of the services. Poverty, inflation, and other economic and market conditions seem almost have not affect the prices of coffins and medicines for the past five years. Under social factors, cultural, norms and religious beliefs affect the purchase of funeral services, though some minority groups have already been encouraged to follow the modern and legal methods of funeral processes. Under technological factors, there are yet many upgrades to be done as far as technological advances are concerned. No automation for the traditional service can replace it as of today. Improving business technology processes increases productivity in the operations. Career attitudes of customers affect the funeral business' profitability by providing information and suggestions on how to improve their services. Under environmental factors, natural phenomenon such as pandemic, weather conditions, and climate change do not greatly affect the funeral business operations because death is inevitable. Under legal factors, being in operation legally ensures the legitimacy of the funeral industry as a legal entity to make profit and pay taxes. Further, it ensures compliance with legal standards for bookkeeping and accounting. This establishes that the funeral industry is paying taxes, employees are covered under adequate insurance, and the business is reporting income to the government. Also, it established consumer trust when a funeral industry is legally operating. A legally operating funeral industry also makes one eligible to receive supplier discounts that one would not normally receive as an unregistered operation.

The challenges of the funeral industry include adherence with the government laws and regulations, inflation, flexibility in the deeply ingrained culture, varied traditions,

beliefs and values, additional secondary services to combat trend, natural calamities and phenomena, and mandated business permits and licenses.

The “Futures Thinking model” anticipates changes and it considers the complexity of the vast internal and external factors that can influence the outcome of a decision and to stay competitive, as in the case of the funeral industry in this study.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were formulated in conformity with the findings and conclusions made:

1. The funeral industry must have a service trademark and commitment to provide family funeral care and services with compassion and understanding to its clients giving meaning to their loss through personalized memorial tributes that truly reflect and celebrate the lives of those who have passed on to eternal life. They should also have testimonials that they have been privileged to have celebrated the lives of distinguished personages as means of advertisements.

2. The funeral industry enjoys financial flexibilities and business sustainability. Since they are very liquid and efficient, it is a determining factor for future research to expand for a new service such as Crematorium Package and upgrading their services. This serves as an alternative option to lessen the cost of memorial services. The funeral industry’s attractiveness is a key factor for investors to help them expand their value chain. Therefore, the investors will feel confident that the funeral industry will grow and make a return on their investment.

3. Transition from traditional funeral service to contemporary funeral service is highly recommended. It is also recommended that funeral industry in Nueva Vizcaya must purchase freezer necessary for soft embalming services to make the bodies more ‘lifelike’ and better suited for contemporary funeral service because the cadaver may be viewed in an open coffin. Also, themed funerals attract more customers with customized preferences for their departed family member. These meaningful occasions with personalized music, a personalized eulogy, symbols, gathering together, and inviting people to participate occasions using symbolic actions usually chosen by the deceased to reflect himself. Innovation of services during the pandemic is recommended. During pandemic and future natural phenomena, the funeral industry should offer individualized services that need emotional considerations from the services other than the traditional services to have a dignified burial. The potential rise of crematorium is an element of contemporary funerals that include themed funeral and its “novelty” for Chinese funeral, Indian funeral, and Muslims funeral to have a respectful funeral based on their respective culture and practices. Furthermore, there must be linkages that require partnership between the business parties. Partner agencies may include Insurance and Mortuary Plan companies and private cemeteries because having strong linkages can promote

business efficiency, profit growth, technological advancements, great potential to increase economic opportunity, and managerial capabilities.

4. As a funeral industry, marketing strategies and practices can significantly improve their performance and financial ability. The goal of social media marketing efforts is to engage prospective buyers so they react to and share the information to others. The funeral industry must have new marketing strategies that take advantage of the competitors' weaknesses like 24-hour active Messenger status for inquiry and Facebook page which includes images and prices of packages offered.

5. The proposed "Futures Thinking Model" for the funeral industry would be a tool for a re-engineered service of funeral industry in a direction where they want to, be understood and valued by consumers, and where profitability would increase.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study is approved by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) at Saint Mary's University, Ponce Street, DMM, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya with cellphone number: 09177053041 and email: reb@smu.edu.ph.

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